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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D2.2 CRISTAL Acquisition System Design and Prototype Realization

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission
A-scan	Standalone radar measurement at unique antenna position
Asset	Desirable structural entity (e.g., utility, rebar, etc.)
B-scan	2D subsurface image formed from multiple 1D A-scans
Carriage	Mounting advanced across quadrant during scanning
Cold Store	Unpowered data storage media (e.g., USB, SD card, etc.)
Contact Surface	Exposed aspect of structure an operator can touch
DT	Digital Twin

Dead-Reckoning	Process of joint local/global coordinate feedback
Defect	Undesirable structural entity (e.g., void, crack, corrosion, etc.)
Element	Individual components or processes in system architecture
Elevation (z)	Vertical coordinate measuring decent into lock
FBG	Fibre Bragg grating
Feature/Feature of Interest	Collective term for structural assets and defects
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensor
Global Coordinates	Geolocated position data (e.g., Lat./Long. or North./East.)
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
Hot Store	Powered data storage media (e.g., server, etc.)
Hybrid Rotational Radar	Sister technology from Rail Tunnel Inspection
Impulse	Time domain radar measurement principal
Length (x)	Long-side coordinate of lock parallel to waterway
Local Coordinates	Displacement relative to local origin of SIR system
ML	Machine Learning
MMI	Machine-Machine Interface
Module	Secondary system subdivision, a collective of units
Normal	3D orientation of vector perpendicular to a specific object
OS	Operating System
Penetrative Depth (r)	Extent of subsurface imaging behind contact surface
Perpendicular	2D orientation at 90° to a specific reference
Prism2	Proprietary radar measurement software by Rad. Sys. Ltd.
Quadrant Area	2D wall coverage of SIR system at specific placement in lock
Quadrant Volume	3D cuboidal region of space behind quadrant area
RAM	Random Access Memory for PC multitasking performance

RAM	Random Access Memory for PC multitasking performance
Raw Measurement	As recorded, without the addition of data analytics
Required Data	Input data required prior to SIR survey undertaking
Return Data	Output data from SIR survey undertaking
RTK GNSS	Real Time Kinematic Global Navigation Satellite System
SB	Smart Buoy
Scanning Trajectory	Path of carriage advance in 2D space
SCMS	Syncromodal Corridor Management System
Serpentine Curve	Time-efficient scanning trajectory in 2D grid pattern
SFCW	Step Frequency Continuous Wave (frequency domain radar)
SFF	Small Form Factor
SIR	Sub-surface Inspection Radar
Subsystem	Primary system subdivision, a collective of modules
Time-Slicing	Process returning 2D slices of 3D radar measurement data
UI/GUI	User Interface /Graphical User Interface
Unit	Tertiary system subdivision, a collective of elements
VNA	Vector Network Analyser
Void-Washout	Mechanism for void growth behind lock chamber walls
Width (y)	Short-side coordinate of lock perpendicular to length

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.2, following up on Deliverable D2.1, describes the prototype realization of CRISTAL system technologies, namely Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS), Smart Buoy System (SB), Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR), Acoustic Emission System (AE) conceived and developed to enhance the waterway navigability and to support predictive maintenance of the different engineered assets that are instrumental to inland waterways (IWW) functionality.

D2.2 details the CRISTAL sensor systems, made up of sensor-based components comprising sensor data acquisition and processing functions. In fact, the CRISTAL data acquisition system is not longer conceived as a separate component of CRISTAL architecture. In each CRISTAL sensor-based system data management functions are embedded allowing, starting from sensor raw data, to provide elaborated data to the Digital Twin (DT) and the Synchronodal Corridor Management Systems (SCMS); both the Synchronodal Corridor Management Systems (SCMS) and Digital Twins (DT) integrate a generic data management system as briefly outlined in this Deliverable.

Data exchange between CRISTAL sensor technologies and other components, such as the Synchronodal Corridor Management Systems (SCMS) and Digital Twins (DT), follows a JSON format. A backend system, referred to as Data Broker, facilitates data and information exchange among these components.

Different partners have been involved in the realization of CRISTAL sensor system technologies and therefore in the editing of deliverable D2.2, as outlined below.

- **CRISTAL technologies for monitoring the navigability conditions of IWW**, namely:
 - **Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS)** for the real time and continuous monitoring of the navigability conditions in free-flowing waterways. FOS System is under realization and testing by the ENEA team. An overview on the conceptual design and working principle of the FOS system and on the components used along with the steps undertaken for realizing the FOS System is presented in D2.2. A proof of concept of the FOS system is as well presented via a laboratory test whose results confirmed the effectiveness of FOS to detect, in real time, the accumulation of sand-dunes and debris that might impare or create issues to the navigability.
 - **Smart Buoy System (SB)** for the continuous and real time monitoring of river navigability and vessel traffic is under realization by the L-PIT team. D2.2 provide a description on how the Smart Buoy System has been realized by assembling different components all commercially available at TRL 9 as well as
- **CRISTAL technologies for predictive and preventive maintenance of IWW engineered infrastructures**, with particular focus on locks' metallic gates and locks' reinforced concrete walls.
 - **Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR)** for checking conditions and possible degradation of lock walls (e.g. material degradation, water ingresses, voids, conditions of reinforcement rods, etc.) is under realization and testing by the UNEW and EUMO teams who provided, as part of D2.2, the conceptual design and working principle of the SIR System along with the detailed description of the SIR system architecture and datasets. UNEW and EUMO touched also on the already on-going work towards the implementation of the SIR Prototype in the French River Pilot.

- **Acoustic Emission System (AE)** for monitoring the conditions of lock gates in controlled waterways is under realization by CERTH who contributed in D2.2 a section on the prototype realization of the AE focusing on the description of the actual design of the AE system with some minor extensions on the already on-going work towards on validation and testing in the French and Italian River Pilots. The tests will be concluded in full as part of Task 2.3 and therefore will be fully described in D2.3.
- **CRISTAL Data Management System**, including CRISTAL Data Store Architecture and CRISTAL Data Set Structure have been detailed by FHG and CERTH; these components will be further developed and implemented in the SCMS and DT, as part of Task 5.2 and therefore will be fully described in D5.2
- **CRISTAL End-Users Interfaces** greatly realized by the FHG team who contributed the related content included in D2.2.

1.1. Introduction

Deliverable 2.2 details the CRISTAL sensor systems, made up of sensor-based components comprising sensor data acquisition and processing functions for:

- monitoring the navigability conditions of IWW,
- monitoring and supporting the predictive and preventive maintenance of IWW engineered infrastructures,
- data integration and processing,
- CRISTAL end-user interfaces including ad-hoc defined dashboards.

Figure 1 illustrates the target CRISTAL System Architecture as an evolution of the CRISTAL System Architecture presented in D2.1. Figure 1 shows that all CRISTAL technologies will interact by exchanging messages through a Data Broker. However, as explained in details in the following sections, full decoupling of the data source and data consumer components will be gradually achieved, starting from direct connections.

The internal architecture of each CRISTAL sensor system is presented in the following sub-sections, along with details on the conceptual design, working principle and realization of the sensor technologies. For some of the sensor-based systems, an example of message structure is also provided.

All the data exchanged between the CRISTAL components will be structured in the JSON format. The Data Broker technology will be selected from those already available, e.g. Rabbit MQ or MQTT broker implementations. Finally, the architecture and technologies for a data management system, that will also be implemented in the SCMS and DT.

WP2 is achieving the aforementioned realizations thanks to the several activities included in 4 Tasks, all led by ENEA, where different partners are successfully contributing as outlined in Tables 1 and 2 in the following sections.

Figure 1 CRISTAL Architecture

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 provides an overview of the alignment of Deliverable 2.2 to the formal deliverable and to the corresponding task descriptions included in the Grant Agreement (GA).

Table 1 Alignment of D2.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.2 CRISTAL acquisition system design and prototype realization	D2.2 provides a proof of concept of CRISTAL sensor-based technologies, in particular: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRISTAL Navigability sensor • CRISTAL Sensors for the resilient management of engineered IWW infrastructures 	Section 2. CRISTAL Technologies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section 2.1 Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS) • Section 2.2 Smart Buoy System (SB) • Section 2.3 Sub Surface Inspection Radar System (SIR) • Section 2.4 Acoustic Emission System (AE) 	<i>Description & Proof of Concept proven to the pilots for laboratory testing as required by MS4 to be completed by M18</i>
	D2.2 provides a proof of CRISTAL the data acquisition system of CRISTAL sensor-based technologies		
	D2.2 presents a prototype of software architecture of the CRISTAL technology platform, in particular: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> architecture of the data-store system structure of the selected data sets. D2.2 provides a proof of end-users interfaces	Section 3. Cristal Data Management System <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.1 CRISTAL Data Store Architercture • 3.2 CRISTAL Data Set Structure • 3.2 CRISTAL End-user interfaces 	
TASKS			
Task 2.1 Technologies for improving the resilient and	The Task will develop technologies enabling the collection of reliable and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section 2.1 Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS) 	<i>Description & Proof of Concept proven to the pilots for laboratory testing as required by</i>

reliable navigability	easy-to-process bed level data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Section 2.2 Smart Buoy System (SB) 	<i>MS4 to be completed by M18</i>
Task 2.2 Technologies for the resilient management of engineered IWW infrastructures	The Task will develop sensors to support health monitoring and preventive resilient management of IWW engineered structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Section 2.3 Sub Surface Inspection Radar System (SAR) Section 2.4 Acoustic Emission System (AE) 	<i>Description & Proof of Concept proven to the pilots for laboratory testing as required by MS4 to be completed by M18</i>
Task 2.3 Software architecture of CRISTAL acquisition system	The Task will develop an innovative cloud-based framework able to acquire, store and elaborate sensor data. CRISTAL acquisition system will be capable to gather multimedia contents, coming from any sensors, including already existing sensors in use by the pilots and the newly developed ones from CRISTAL project. CRISTAL cloud layer service will be provided to the pilots, as a web-server solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1 CRISTAL Data Store Architecture 3.2 CRISTAL Data Set Structure 	<i>Description & Proof of Concept proven to the pilots for laboratory testing as required by MS4 to be completed by M18</i>
Task 2.4 End-users interfaces including ad-hoc defined dashboards and mobile Apps for navigability, preventive maintenance as well as to support corridor management	This task will enable the customisation of CRISTAL GUI end-user interfaces (GUI graphical user interface) for use in IWW allowing also end-users to query databases and to check results of simulations. Ad-hoc mobile applications will also be developed for a user-friendly and effective representation of the KPIs proposed in the framework of CRISTAL project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.3 CRISTAL End-Users Interfaces 	<i>Description & Proof of Concept proven to the pilots for laboratory testing as required by MS4 to be completed by M18</i>

Table 2 provides the list of authors and CRISTAL partners that greatly contributing to the writing and editing of Deliverable 2.2.

Table 2 Authors and contributing partners for Deliverable D2.2

Section	Contributing Partner/s	Authors by affiliation
Section 1. Introduction	ENEA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sonia Giovinazzi • Maria Luisa Villani
Section 2.1 Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS)	ENEA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michele Caponero • Cristina Mazzotta
Section 2.2 Smart Buoy (SB)System	L-PIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomasz Markowski
Section 2.3 Sub Surface Inspection Radar System(SIR)	UNEW EUMO	<p>In addition to Paul and I, please consider the following co-authors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cristian Ulianov (UNEW) • Paul Hyde (UNEW) • Thomas McDonald (UNEW) • Mark Robinson (UNEW) • Simon Hartshorne (EUMO)
Section 2.4 Acoustic Emission System (AE)	CERTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tsenis Theocharis • Charis Kourousia
Section 3.1 CRISTAL Data Store Architercture	FHG CERTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Krämer, Björn (FHG) • Rademacher, Rebecca (FHG) • Tsenis Theocharis (CERTH)
Section 3.2 CRISTAL Data Set Structure	CERTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tsenis Theocharis (CERTH) • Tomasz Markowski (L-PIT)
Section 3.3 CRISTAL End-user interfaces	FHG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Krämer, Björn (FHG) • Rademacher, Rebecca (FHG)
Section 4. Conclusions	All above-mentioned partners	All above-mentioned authors

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into four main chapters. Further to this introduction, Section 2 details the CRISTAL sensor systems, made up of sensor-based components comprising sensor data acquisition and processing functions. Section 3 outlines the architecture and technologies for a data management system, including CRISTAL Data Store Architecture and CRISTAL Data Set Structure that will be implemented in both the Digital Twins (DT) and the Synchronodal Corridor Management Systems (SCMS). Section 3 presents, as well, CRISTAL End-user interfaces. Section 4 briefly summarizes the conclusion and the planned next steps.

2. CRISTAL Technologies

2.1. CRISTAL Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS)

2.1.1 FOS Conceptual design and working principle

The working principle of the FOS System is based on the detection of the accumulation of debris such as sand, pebbles, etc. by weighing pads permanently installed on the riverbed. Fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are used to instrument the weighing pads. FBG sensors are intrinsic FOS sensors: their mode of operation is based on the disturbance of the light occurring inside the fibre with no need of neither additional external devices nor externally supplied energy.

FBG sensors are a specific type of FOS Sensors based on the FBG technology are adopted because of some of its specific features, namely

- no need of power supply at the sensing location.
- long term stability in quasi-static measurement regime.
- cabling requirements fully compatible with standard solutions developed for submerged and offshore fibre optic networks. A set of FBG sensors is considered at each pad in order to perform the bending measurement in differential-mode and with temperature-compensation procedures. Both strain (bending) and temperature measurements can be done by FBG sensors.

The principle of operation of the FBG sensors is here briefly recalled. A comprehensive presentation of the FBG technology can be found in the literature (for a pioneer classic paper, see 'A. Othonos, Fiber Bragg gratings, Rev. Sci. Instrum. 68 (1997) 4309'). FBG sensors are embedded in the core of the optical fibre, with no alteration of the size and structure of the fibre itself, and they do not necessitate power supply at the sensing location. FBG gratings are produced as diffraction gratings in a short segment of an optical fibre. The production occurs by a periodic variation of the refractive index of the core of the optical fibre, with no evident alteration of its dimension and appearance. The rest of the fibre stays pristine and operates for the transmission of sensor's signal. If broadband light propagates along the fibre, a specific narrowband back-propagating signal originates at the FBG grating by diffraction. The central wavelength of the signal is linearly dependent on the strain and temperature of the FBG grating. Thus, if the FBG grating is put in structural or thermal contact with a component, it can be operated as an FBG strain or

temperature sensor, with the value of the parameter of interest being encoded in the spectroscopic analysis of the FBG signal. Figure 2 shows an FBG and a schematic representation of the dependence of its spectroscopic signal on strain and temperature.

Figure 2 FBG and schematic representation of the dependence of its spectroscopic signal on strain and temperature.

To measure parameters different from strain and temperature, the FBG grating can be functionalized (i.e., made indirectly sensitive to the wanted parameter) by use of a proper transducer. For instance: embedding the FBG grating in a hygroscopic material, humidity can be monitored via the strain of the FBG grating resulting by the swelling of that material. Commercial FBG sensors have been developed for a variety of mechanical, environment and biochemical parameters, with full coverage of all common requirements for any application in the civil engineering field.

Many FBG gratings can stay along the same optical fibre and can be operated in wavelength division multiplexing (WDM), as shown in Figure 3. In fact, the signal of an FBG grating can be considered a narrowband selective reflection of the broadband light launched into the fibre. Thus, the light wavelengths not reflected by an FBG grating keeps propagating along the fibre and can be used for other FBG gratings. To apply WDM, two basic constraints apply: i) absence of overlapping of the different signals, also considering the wavelength shifts that occur during the measurement; ii) allocation of all the signals within the band of the light launched into the fibre. As a basic reference: i) FBG-interrogation systems have a broadband of 80 nm, and a wavelength shift resolution of 1 pm; ii) FBG gratings have an intrinsic sensitivity of 1 pm per 0.1°C and 1 pm per microStrain.

Figure 3 Schematic representation of an array of FBG sensors and its WDM working principle.

Since the signal of the FBG grating is sensitive to both temperature and strain, to perform strain measurement a thermal compensation is necessary. In fact, structural contact usually implicates thermal contact, so that the total signal is the sum of a strain signal and a thermal signal. Thermal compensation can be easily done by use of two companion FBG sensors, one in structural contact (e.g., by glue) and the other one in thermal contact only (e.g., by thermal fluid paste), by subtracting the signal of the latter from the signal of the former.

A schematic representation of the proposed installation is given in Figure 4. Weighing pads permanently installed on the riverbed detect the accumulation of sand, pebbles, etc. The weighing pads operate according to the bending plate principle: a mass causes a bending deformation of the plate, which in turn causes a strain of the plate surfaces related to the weight of the mass. In the proposed installation, the strain is measured by use of FBG strain sensors.

Figure 4 Schematic representation of the proposed FOS System Technology.

The adopted bending plate operation principle provides a weighing pad with no moving parts and consequent benefit for the system's durability. Multiple FBG sensors are envisaged to instrument each pad: i) at least one FBG to perform temperature compensation; ii) a set of strain FBGs to provide an adequately precise deformation surface mapping as necessary to manage the expected uneven mass distribution over the plate. Weighing pads are installed at selected locations along in the riverbed. Locations are selected according to the past knowledge and predictive analysis of the formation of debris accumulation along the waterway. As an example, an installation with multiple weighing pads along the full cross section of the river is shown in Figure 4.

2.1.2 FOS Realization

It is envisaged that the weighing pads shall be installed buried in the ground, surfacing the floor of the riverbed. Considerations about the correct and safe installation, mainly with respect to the natural instability of the riverbed floor and the possible dredging activity, are addressing possible solutions for an engineered design which shall be done at a later stage. The top surface of the pad acts as the actual weighing plate, experiencing a bending deformation because of the mass resting on it. The bending deformation of the plate is measured by the set of the FBG sensors that are installed on its bottom surface.

The working principle of the bending plate for weighing application is given in Figure 5 (top left): a sheet of finite width is subject to strain of opposite sign on the two opposite surfaces. The value of the strain depends on the acting force and its mapping over the surface depends on, the constrains (simple support, ...), the acting force (direction, distribution, ...), the material of the sheet. Considering homogeneous materials and simple constrains, the mechanical model is simple and can be easily solved by mathematical and numerical methods. Figure 5 (bottom left) shows a FEM computation of the strain of a two-side simply supported plate subject to normal force evenly distributed on a large footprint centred on the plate surface. Figure 5 (right) shows three examples of strain mapping at different force position and force footprint.

Figure 5 Working principle of the weighing bending plate (left, top) and strain map of a plate supported along the two long sides with and loaded with different force footprint.

No commercial FBG-based weighing pad systems for submerged applications exist. A pad prototype has been designed by the ENEA team, relaying on the expertise gained in previous activities devoted to the development of weighing pads, based on bending plates, for railway and automotive traffic control. Figure 6 shows an experimental setup and data from activities of the completed research project SENTINEL (funded Italian Ministry MIUR - action PNR 2015-2020 ARS01_00243), aiming at the development of bending plates for automotive traffic weighing. Picture in Figure 6 show the plate instrumented with seven FBGs, simply supported along the two long sides and subject to calibration measurement by a press. The graph on the left shows the timeline signal from the seven FBG sensors, as the force was applied repeatedly. The graph on the right shows the spectral signal from the seven FBG sensors at different force values.

Figure 6 Pictures show a bending weighing plate instrumented with seven FBGs and the test setup. Graphs show the timeline of the signal at different force values (left) and the spectral signal (right).

Figure 7 shows a sketch of the prototype produced for the proof-of-concept activity. A simple design was adopted: rectangular bending plate and rectangular basement, with linear contact constrain along two opposite sides. Aluminium was used for the basement and the plate. Brass was used for the linear contact rails. As better specified further, the choice of the materials and methods to produce a system suitable for long-term working life in the expected environment can be easily addressed by industrial solutions developed in use for maritime/offshore constructions and for power/data submerged/submarine cabling.

Figure 7 Schematic representation of the prototype produced for the proof-of-concept activity.

A simple design was adopted: rectangular bending plate and rectangular basement, with linear contact constrain along two opposite sides. Aluminium was used for the basement and the plate, brass was used for the linear contact rails.

The choice of the materials and methods for the production of a system suitable for real application and long-term working life in the expected environment can be easily addressed by industrial solutions developed in use for maritime/offshore constructions and for power/data submerged/submarine cabling.

A maintenance-free working condition along the full working life can be reliably assumed. The choice of the design of the pad, based on the bending plate principle, was addressed by the following considerations about maintenance and prevention of failure, although specific engineering solutions (at this stage conceptually given in Figure 3) will have to be worked out at a later stage.

- The design considers a plate simply supported. That makes the mechanics particularly simple. No moving parts, springs, leverages, and cinematic chains are necessary. Relative movements only occur at the constrain, which are of the simple support type with rotation freedom (hinge). No specific maintenance for the mechanical components shall be envisaged assuming construction with commercially available stainless steel qualified for submersed application.
- The installation of the FBG sensors on the plate is done by mean of structural epoxy glue. That technique is derived by the composite materials industry and provides commercial solutions fully proved for severe applications and in hostile environment with working life longer than 30 years.

The working life of optical fibre and FBG sensors is much longer than 30 years, using standard materials available for telecommunication undersea installation (FBG sensors have the same technology that fibre gratings for telecommunication notch filters).

- A sealed construction/enclosure is envisaged, to avoid debris to accumulate under the bending plate and obstruct the free bending of the plate.
- The maintenance plan reduces to inspection and countermeasures for limescale crust of the system, whose recurrence in not-salted moving water is quite low and slow if any.

The bending plate was instrumented with three FBG sensors, all oriented with their measuring axis parallel to the bending line, normal to the contact constrain lines. Figure 8 shows a picture of the bottom surface of the plate with the three sensors. Figure 8 also shows an expanded view of one sensor, stuck with structural epoxy resin. The sensor is embedded in the central resin drop. The two side resin drops hold in place the protective tubing in which the fibre is inserted for routing toward the measuring instrument.

Figure 8 Bending plate instrumented with three FBG sensors and enlarged view of one of the sensors.

The plate was tested and calibrated on a testbench in dry by use of multiple reference masses. Figure 9 shows the testbench and two steps of the repeated step-by-step load/unload procedure.

Figure 9 Testbench and two-step step-by-step load/unload procedure.

2.1.3 FOS Proof of Concept

In the setup configuration shown in Figure 9, the system was also used to workout data processing algorithm intended to optimize measurements introducing temperature compensation, and filtering of other transitory disturbances. Disturbances were produced as both thermal and mechanical controlled excitation. Thermal disturbances were produced as both fast transitory by heating lamp, and as low gradients by changing the conditioned temperature in the laboratory. Mechanical disturbances were produced by uncontrolled vibrations produced with rotating machinery placed on purpose on the testbench. The processing algorithm operates in real time and is mainly based on differential measurements worked out with different combination of the signal of the three FBG sensors. In subtraction mode the differential signal provides a mean for thermal compensation, which is a feature considered critical to the intended application. Running average of single and differential signals is also considered. The development of the processing algorithm is to be considered as preliminary and to be optimised with respect to true disturbances signatures as deemed for the installation site. A possible improvement will possibly consider the use of extra FBG sensors installed with no structural adhesion to the bending plate, to provide either pure temperature measurement or accelerometric (vibration) measurement of the supporting plate (soil).

Figure 10 shows the result of a step-by-step load/unload test. Raw data from the three FBGs are reported in the top graph, showing their finely correlated response to the resting mass variation. The mean value of the individual measurements is reported in the middle graph. Using the mean value reduces the dependence from the position over the plate where the mass rests, which in the intended application has correspondence with the expected uneven accumulation of debris on the plate surface. Some filtering based on temporary trend of the signal is applied to go to the result shown in the bottom graph. That filtering corrects for relaxation effects, which are seen and can be physically expected from both the plate and the resin/fibre interface.

Figure 10 Results of the step-by-step load/unload test.

As an outcome of the above reported results, suggestions about a best choice of the coating of the FBG sensors arose. FBG sensors with acrylate coating were used, getting an excessive relaxation effect, although within elastic and repeatable behaviour. Use of FBG with polyimide coating will cancel that effect, easing the optimization of the data processing algorithm to face the relaxation effect of the metal material. The use of some special material different from aluminium will be considered for the bending plate, to improve the stability of the elastic performance with respect of an expected prevalent long term slowly varying and quasi-steady load condition (standard sediment accumulation) interleaved with occasional abrupt load increase/decrease (unusual and exceptional water flow events).

The prototype was prepared for submerged tests, protecting the installed sensors by waterproofing coating. Here a medium industrial-grade product for unsalted mild water was used, but a large variety of commercial products and industrial solutions exist for virtually any type of chemically aggressive and submerged conditions. Figure 11 shows the protection of the optical fibre that was realized with standard materials for cabling in sewer conducts, which offer a high endurance in aggressive and non-chemical inert liquids. The ingress of the protective tubing is protected by the waterproofing coating. As for the above consideration about the waterproofing coating, adequate industrial solutions for the final intended application are available and will be considered in the future activity devoted to the construction of the engineered prototype.

Figure 11 Results of the step-by-step load/unload test.

The setup was used for the proof-of-concept activity: the prototype was laid on the bottom of the tank; the prototype stayed submerged in the tank and coarse sand was progressively poured on it. Figure 12 shows a view with turbid water soon after some sand pouring, and with sand build-up through clear water. As the system in this proof-of-concept configuration is not provided of any sealing protective enclosure (as conceptually shown in Figure 3), it was covered with a soft plastic sheet to avoid debris running between the bending plate and the supporting basement. The testbed was prepared in a conditioned hall, to allow control of the water temperature by equilibrium with the environment temperature. Tap water was used for the progressive filling of the tank, with no possibility to control its temperature. Standard commercial thermometers were used to monitor the temperature of the air and the temperature of the water in the tank.

The pouring of the sand was done adopting various procedures, with both massive abrupt drops and gentle progressive pouring. The test was finalized to verify the capability of the system to detect the mass increase, waiving at this stage the implementation of any procedures devoted to estimate the high of the sand build-up.

Figure 12 Testbed and some test steps, from top-left to bottom-right: a view of the setup; the bending plate in the tank; turbid water soon after some sand pouring; a sand build-up through clear water.

The proof-of-concept test was done introducing temperature perturbations to be accounted for by data processing, following and optimising algorithms previously developed in other research projects aiming at the development of FBG sensors for structural and environmental monitoring (deformation, relative humidity, temperature). Optimisation was addressed by specific procedures developed and applied in the above mentioned project SENTINEL (funded Italian Ministry MIUR - action PNR 2015-2020 ARS01_00243) in which were developed weighing devices based on use of FBG sensors and the bending plate technology.

Figure 13 shows raw and processed data from a continuous acquisition lasted longer than seven days. Three graphs are shown.

- Raw data (top graph) show continuous variation due to temperature variation of the water, coming from both temperature variation of the environment and additional filling of the tank with tap water.
- Four tracks are shown, named in the legend. The very raw data come from the three FBG sensors. Their values differ because each sensor measures the local deformation at its own position, and the mapping of the plate depends on the shape of the sand pile-up. Evaluation of the mean value is an effective procedure to produce a signal coherently related to the total quantity of the mass of the sand pile-up.
- Improvement of the procedure, to be worked out at a later stage and in a more significant setup, will take into account parameters as for instance: i) averaging weight of the signal of the individual FBG sensors, depending on the position of the sensor on the surface of the plate and with respect to the distance from the constraints; ii) mean value of the expected material density, to move from mass to height of the pile-up, which is the parameter of interest for the safe navigability.
 - Applying the temperature compensation procedure, the temperature signal is finely suppressed (middle graph). The processing leaves in place the running signal variation not due to temperature variation, thus providing evidence of the running increase of the sand mass laying on the plate. The height of the spikes is related to the quantity of the added mass.
- Temperature compensation relies on the differential signal of the three sensors, which is null for the temperature excitation, being the three sensors in thermal equilibrium on a low thermal impedance material. Temperature compensation is applied on the raw FBGmean signal, evaluated as specified above and shown in the top graph.
- Improvement of the temperature compensation is envisaged by use of one additional FBG sensor in pure thermal contact with the bending plate (free structural contact in thermal grease). That will be worked out at a later stage and in a more significant setup.
 - Applying integration of the running signal variation, the absolute signal variation is obtained (bottom graph), with evidence of the absolute quantity of mass laying on the plate.
- Integration in time is a forward processing method, and was here adopted with no correction procedures. In view of the real application, additional procedures shall be considered to limit the error building which affects any integrative measurement. It is envisaged to adopt absolute reference procedures to be worked out at a later stage, also relying on independent periodic (annual or other long term) measurements as water column depth by sonar probe.

In Figure 13 the timeline extends from the morning of the first day ($t < 0.5$) till the afternoon of the eighth day ($t > 7.5$).

- Till about time $t = 1.5$ the signal increase is due to the cooling due to the temperature of the water.
- At time about $t = 1.5$ the abrupt increase is due to a massive sand drop
- In between time $t = 2.3$ and $t = 2.6$ modest and similar sand drops occurred
- At time about $t = 5.6$ a modest sand drop occurred

- The trend till time about $t=2.3$ refers to the main thermalisation of the plate in the poored water
- The trend after time about $t=3$ refers to thermalisation of the water in the lab environment (cooling was done on purpose at time about $t=5.3$, as disturbance of the planned sand drop done at time about $t=5.6$)

Figure 13 Row and processed data from a continuous acquisition lasted about seven days. In the abscissa time is given in day (24h).

After the test reported in Figure 13, various tests were repeated with addition and subtraction of sand on the plate either at regular or irregular time intervals. Figure 14 shows the timeline of actions done in a period some longer than 48 hours. The graph shows the temperature compensated integrated signal, related to the total mass of sand resting on the plate. Incremental (decremental) steps on the graph correspond to addition (subtraction) of sand. The height of the steps is related to the mass of sand added or removed.

Figure 14 FOS integrated signal (total mass resting on the plate) of repeated and various addition and subtraction of sand. In the abscissa time is given in day (24h).

Results from the experimental activity done for the proof-of-concept confirm the suitability of the proposed design for the intended application. Further experimental activity, to be carried out at the next stages of the project, is needed to assess the suitability in a relevant environment. Within the available resources of the project, an engineered prototype will be produced and tested in a large basin (waiving for running water) and with relevant debris pile-up.

- Reliability of the evaluation of pile-up high from weighted mass: mass weighing error; error of high estimation with respect to the variability of debris type and estimated density.
- Engineering issues: enclosure of the pad and cable penetration sealing; number and geometric disposition of the FBG sensors instrumenting the plate; material and design/finishing of the plate and of the constrains.
- Mechanical issues: structures of the plate and constrains, useful working measure range and protection from accidental overload/impact and riverbed dredging.

Information from the FOS system integrate in the general data management system. The specific contribution of the FOS system is addressed to mapping the pile-up high at the critical locations, to monitor the depth of the water for safe navigability (after integration with water level data). Special and relevant contribution for navigability is expected by data about pile-up fast changes after extreme climatic events, for both real time information (pile-up production/displacement due to water overflow, etc.) and projections in near/far future (pile-up growing rate and displacements related to waterflow variations, etc.).

Data from the FOS system find integration in the general data management and Digital twin model (Reference Section). The processing and integration workflow can be summarized as in the following.

- FBG sensors provide optical raw data, delivered by fibre optic cable to a datalogger.
- Raw data are converted in engineering data (pile-up height) by on-board processing at the datalogger.
- Engineered data are transmitted to the data broker (Fig. XX) for integration and decision making.

2.2. CRISTAL Smart Buoy System (SB)

2.2.1 SB Conceptual design and working principle

Crstal Smart Buoy System was conceived to ensure the implementation the following functionalities:

- measure river's parameters
 - ✓ the river depth in the selected location - under the buoy
 - ✓ the clearance under the bridge
 - ✓ water temperature
 - ✓ water speed
 - ✓ current water direction

- measure weather conditions
 - ✓ air temperature
 - ✓ air pressure
 - ✓ wind speed
 - ✓ wind direction.
- monitor the river's traffic and establish communication with vessels:
 - ✓ counting passing ships
 - ✓ module for vessel communication

To meet these requirements, a market review was carried out in search of existing sensors that would, on the one hand, ensure measurement of the indicated parameters and, on the other hand, ensure operation in an environment with low availability of a power source - in this case, powering the sensors based on renewable energy sources.

At the same time, legal regulations regarding the implementation of buoys on inland water ways were reviewed, and during talks with the infrastructure manager, existing data sources and possibilities of cooperation in the field of the implementation and operation of intelligent river buoys were identified.

After determining that the existing buoys managed by Wody Polskie do not have the appropriate buoyancy to support the proposed set of sensors, a decision was made to design a solution based on buoys with greater buoyancy, the shape and size of which were selected to reflect the estimated required buoyancy related to the weight and size of the embedded devices.

In addition to monitoring data transmission from the intelligent buoy, emergency situations are also supervised. For the construction of the buoy, it was assumed that the buoy would be resistant to the pressure of obstacles carried by the river current weighing up to 150 kg. When this weight is exceeded, the anchor lines will break - the buoy's displacement will be detected by changing the buoy's GPS location, and the transmitted location will be the basis for locating and recovering the smart buoy. If the buoy floods, the possibility of data transmission will be limited, which will result in the previously described alert about the lack of data from the buoy and the need to service the intelligent buoy.

2.2.2 SB Realization

In the tender processes, in accordance with the regulations in force in Poland for public entities, the different buoy elements were obtained through a tender as reported in Table 3.

Table 3 Smart Buoy Components and their service functions

Smart Buoy Components	SB components' service functions
DST810 Smart™ Multisensor with Gen2 Paddlewheel	river depth in the selected location - under the buoy clearance under the bridge water temperature

	<p>speed-through-water and speed resolution</p> <p>integrated attitude sensor for heel and trim data</p> <p>pitch&roll</p>
AIRMAR Weather Station 200WX - wind speed & direction, air temp & humidity	<p>air temperature , humidity, air pressure , wind speed, wind direction.</p> <p>Meteorological Station Data</p> <p>dynamic true wind speed and direction based upon the apparent wind</p> <p>GNSS data, Data&Time, Magnetic Variation, Attitude</p> <p>Rate of Turn, Vessel Heading</p> <p>Position and Rapid Update</p> <p>COG and SOG</p> <p>Vessel Speed</p> <p>heading, position, speed-over-ground, and course-over-ground functionality for dynamic true wind-data processing on a moving vessel</p>
RR30.DAO0-GGPI.9VF Radar distance measuring sensors	Buoy-vessel distance measuring sensors
TF03-100 LiDAR 0,5 deg angle*	measuring variable distances via Light Detection and Ranging,LiDAR
Leddar IS16*	<p>o detect, locate and measure all types of objects that are either solid or liquid. The IS16 industrial</p> <p>Leddar™ sensor provides both distance and angular positioning while performing continuous</p> <p>analysis of the area. Specifically designed for the industrial market, this unique sensor is optimized</p> <p>for 0 to 50 meter detection and ranging applications.</p>
AIS EM-TRAK R300 RECEIVER*	Dual channel, Automatic Identification System, AIS receiver Receiving all AIS message types

*Optional components

Main elements of the intelligent buoy system communicate based on the CAN bus transmission mechanism (e.g. NMEA2000, IOLINK) as well as UART communication. Therefore, as part of the study, elements enabling communication with this type of bus in the form of a CAN message decoder were purchased. After receiving CAN bus frames, messages from individual sensors are processed and transmitted to the cloud system in the established JSON format..

Figure 15 shows the prototype of the smart buoy and in particular how two of the components, an example of the location of two of the components, i.e. the sensors for measuring the measure weather conditions and river parameters will be embedded in the buoy. Further technical details of the components are provided in Appendix I.

Figure 15 Prototype of CRISTAL smart buoy

A solar panel will to be included in smart buoy prototype (Figure 15) to allow the buoy to operate autonomously. Towards the sizing of the solar panel the power consumption of the different components of the smart buoy system was measured as reported in Table 2.

Table 4 Power consumption of of the different components of the smart buoy system

Smart Buoy Components	Power [W]	Power / day [W]
DST810 Smart™ Multisensor with Gen2 Paddlewheel	2,4	57,6
Meteorological parameters: AIRMAR® 150WX WeatherStation® Instrument	0,9	21,6
Module for vessel communication (AIS)	1,8	43,2

Communication (GSM) module (continuous consumption)	1	24
RR30.DAO0-GGPI.9VF Radar distance measuring sensors	2,4	
Leddar IS16	1,2	
TF03-100 LiDAR 0,5 deg angle	0,96	
Smart Buoy Components	Power [W]	Power / day [W]

Power/day calculation in Table 2 assumes 24 sensor readings per day (1 reading / hour). The total estimated energy consumption for sensor units, GSM communication module and AIS receiver is therefore about 150 Wh per day (precisely 146,5 Wh/day), resulting in 53472 Wh/year and 75 Wp. Based on this the minimum peak power of PV panel should be not less than 75W. Because of construction constrains this power production should be achieved by combining multiple panels rather than from single big one. Combined surface area of PV panels active at the same time should be not less than 0.5 m², to ensure sufficient energy production. We assume that data from all sensors will be provided continuously, in repeatable periods, adjusted to the variability of the measured parameters. To estimate energy demand, it was assumed that individual parameters would be measured at least once an hour, which is in accordance with measurements carried out by water infrastructure managers in Poland at stationary measurement stations.

It was assumed that the developed device would transmit data to an external, cloud-based data collection system in continuous mode, immediately after the measurement, however, due to the location and possible communication difficulties in the operating environment, a local data buffer was provided, allowing for temporary data storage and synchronization in when transmission capabilities become available. Due to the nature of the data and their usefulness mainly in the real-time access mode, there is no justification for long-term data storage, and failure to transfer them within a few or several hours undermines the sense of their processing and means a system failure. Therefore, an alert functionality should be implemented on the cloud system side, allowing for the detection of lack of data from the intelligent buoy at set time intervals, which will allow the implementation of the failure removal procedure.

2.2.3 SB Proof of Concept

All selected components for the construction of an intelligent buoy are commercially available devices and are classified as TRL9. The buoy prototype, consisting of TRL9 devices, will be tested in laboratory and real conditions, in the prototype variant, and as such should be classified as TRL7. An outline of the high-level architecture of the SIR system is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 High level architecture of Smart buoy system (SBS)

In the Polish pilot scenario, where the smart buoy will be used:

- Sensory data provided continuously: sensors on the river buoy (depth, wind direction, temperature, etc.), sensor measuring the clearance under the bridge,
- Data acquired periodically: communication with the module installed on the ship, obtaining data on a given vessel obtained when the vessel passes the buoy
- Data processing: local based on own IT solution
- Data sharing: based on an established common data broker mechanism,

- Recipient of locally processed data: EPCIS, common data broker
- Other data: all data sources will be identified based on the list of needs defined by WP5 and WP3

Section 3.2 provides an example of the structure and information content of data that will be delivered to superior systems, i.e. DT, and indirectly to SCMS. All data generated by sensors located on the intelligent buoy will be transmitted via a broker (probably MQTT) to the digital twin and then to the SCMS system, where, based on recorded changes, information relevant to infrastructure management will be generated.

2.3. CRISTAL Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR)

Locks are engineering structures that facilitate the efficient gradient traversal of thousands of high-capacity vessels across Europe's inland waterways network daily (Eurostat, 2022). Engineering structures are critical parts of inland waterways infrastructure. Their condition is key for ensuring efficient operation on the waterways and crucial for safety in some critical cases. Therefore, appropriate planning and delivery of maintenance activities require good knowledge of structures' condition and of potential damages and/or failures that may develop over time.

Continuously varying stresses, associated with moving traffic and naturally shifting surrounding landmass degrade structural health over time, which may result in the formation of subsurface defects. Without swift detection and intervention, such defects grow rapidly, weakening the strength of lock walls and increasing the likelihood of critical failure (i.e., wall collapse). As locks are inherent network bottlenecks, maximising network efficiency requires minimising avoidable lock closures for repairs. Therefore, more effective targeted maintenance planning, logistics and execution requires comprehensive knowledge of the lock wall subsurface structural condition. Based on knowledge achieved through previously developed applications for other industries, a radar-based system was designed for the subsurface inspection of IWW assets, particularly for concrete structures such as those of critical assets like locks or dams.

Relevant use-cases have been identified and presented in the deliverable report D2.1 (CRISTAL, 2023). The development the SIR system in the CRISTAL project is focusing on customising the technology for specific application to large-scale concrete infrastructure on Europe's inland waterways network, principally lock walls.

The Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) transmits radio-frequency pulses into lock walls, which partially backscatter from subsurface features of interest (e.g., voids, reinforcement rods, water ingress, etc.). With suitable interpretation, the duration and intensity of reflected pulses inform feature presence, spatial-profiles, and material properties. Further processing of the 3D imagery of subsurface features of interest can be returned to inform the stakeholder (IWW infrastructure manager, or entity in charge of maintenance) in relation to any required maintenance activities.

Lock walls are sheer vertical structures and inspection windows are limited to several days only; therefore, conventional handheld radar-based scanners (e.g., Screening Eagle, 2023; GSSI, 2023) requiring time-consuming gantry setup, gantry re-location and hand-driven movement are not viable in this context. A system for swift and comprehensive recovery of 3D feature profiles from raw SIR data is essential, which

should also be capable of interfacing and communicating with the platforms of the digital solutions (Digital Twin and Synchronodal Corridor Management System) being developed in the CRISTAL project.

Considering the overall role of SIR technology in applications as described above, four key challenges for the development process in the CRISTAL project have been identified:

- System design for application to vertical lock wall structures with limited and restricted accessibility.
- System design for maximal efficiency, and automated data acquisition.
- System design for effective 3D feature recovery.
- System design for communication and compatibility with the CRISTAL digital platforms.

The following subsections detail the phases carried out for design and implementation of the SIR system prototype to date, based upon use cases discussed in deliverable D2.1 and subsequent requirements identified or generated therein.

2.3.1 Architecture of Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR)

An outline of the high-level architecture of the SIR system is presented in Figure 17. **Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania..** The system is divided first into two major “Subsystems”, which are further subdivided in “Modules”, at the secondary level, and “Units”, at the tertiary level, with each unit formed from one or more constituent “Elements”, i.e., specific components or processes that address a key task of the SIR system. Due to the complexity and interconnectedness of the developing SIR system architecture, the display of all key elements in the same diagram proved impractical for legibility and reporting clarity, therefore the diagram in Figure 17 a simplified high-level architecture, which shows just the major constituents, while specifics of element to element communications, physical interface types and power routing across the system, and other details are presented in the technical breakdowns provided below.

In spanning both physical and virtual environments, with a complex network of interactions across and within constituents, the complexity is inherent to the 3D visualisation of SIR datasets, both from a data acquisition and processing perspective. Complexity has further arisen from the logistics and practicalities at different development stages (from design to implementation of prototype), which has been motivated by focus on ensuring the required versatility of the SIR system is delivered. To date, the development of this architecture must consider and find specific solutions for multiple **key interfaces**, including:

- Machine-Machine Interfaces (MMI) between individual elements, units or subsystems respectively;
- Human-Machine Interface (HMI) in areas such as apparatus portability, control hardware interaction and quadrant scan execution, and
- End-User Interface (UI) for system automation and onsite feedback.

In order to avoid confusion and improve communication, and reporting of work already carried out and outcomes achieved, a formal nomenclature has been adopted by the SIR development team, relating to items both in the physical and digital domain for the lock structures and execution of SIR inspection

process. This terminology is used throughout the overall development work, as well as in further sections of this report. Key nomenclature conventions are subsequently detailed.

Terminology used for physical characteristics of a lock structure (from above):

- the “length” of the lock chamber (x) will always denote the extent of the long side of the structure parallel to the waterway;
- the “width” of the lock chamber (y) will always denote the short side of the structure perpendicular to the length;
- the “centre” of the lock chamber is regarded to be the global origin ($\underline{0}$) for the purposes of this report;
- two notions of “depth” were considered in the context of SIR, i.e.:
 - “penetrative depth” of inspection (r), which represents the extent of imaging into the contact surface of inspection interest (i.e., the distance a feature of interest resides behind a specific wall);
 - “lock chamber depth”, which will be here referred to as “elevation” (z) to avoid confusion. This term denotes the vertical descent into the lock chamber, with ground-surface level (at the chamber top) locally at 0m elevation.

Also, it should be noted that the local coordinate reference frame will be aligned to the global coordinate reference frame defined by GNSS standardised Easting/Northing/Elevation values. It has local origin $\hat{\underline{0}}$.

Figure 17 High level architecture of Subsurface Inspection Radar system (SIR)

Terminology used for execution of inspection

Considering that the length of a European lock frequently exceeds 100m, with lowest elevations downwards of 10m below ground level and crews operating across lock drained structure throughout the inspection window, it is impractical for any substructure inspection system to be designed to span the full lock structure. Therefore, from a physical data acquisition perspective, the proposed SIR system spans a localised rectangular area of the chamber walls termed a survey “quadrant”, which from a data processing viewpoint equates to a localised, regularly gridded cuboidal cloud of data points extending across the chamber wall and into the subsurface, this is the associated survey quadrant “volume” V . In total, the full lock wall structure is subdivided into Q quadrants. An arbitrary survey quadrant Q_i is presented in Figure 18, with relevant nomenclature highlighted in-situ.

Figure 18 Local coordinate geometry of an arbitrary lock chamber wall survey quadrant Q_i and survey volume. V_i

The term “subsurface” of the lock structure refers to any region of the structure concealed behind a physical obstruction (e.g., the wall). The boundary between the surface and the interior of the lock chamber is designated the “contact surface” boundary.

Finally, when referring to 3D visualisations of SIR datasets, the term “feature” collectively denotes both design details of “assets” (expected or desirable subsurface entities such as rebar or buried utilities) and “defects”. A defect is an undesirable imperfection within the subsurface of the lock wall. Defects can take the form of fine cracks and range up to the size of large voids exceeding several meters in span. For lock wall inspection, considering requirements from infrastructure managers, the SIR system is targeting detection of moderately sized voids in excess of the pitch of the rebar within the structure, considered the most serious defect complicating maintenance efforts. Such voids are associated with the infiltration

of water and associated washout of both concrete and corroded steel from the otherwise expected regular grid of rebar, therefore the term “void-washout” was adopted for these defects. Resulting voids are expected to be frequently wrapped around intersections within the rebar mesh extending in all directions both towards and contact surface and further into the subsurface.

2.3.2 Design of Sensor System for Subsurface Inspection of Lock Structure

The design of the radar-based sensor system for subsurface inspection of lock structures was completed and its major subsystems and constituents procured and implemented. However, component selection and tuning of integration solutions for the SIR system is still ongoing at time of writing, for the purpose of design refinement. Nevertheless, sufficient relevant testing and hand-on interaction with each constituent module have confirmed the current design solutions adopted for SIR system module designs, as well as the system capabilities of gathering and returning the required output for the end users. The consolidation of all individual modules into the standalone physical prototype will follow in due course.

The following subsections present a detailed breakdown of system constituents, and the design refinement process is detailed for each key subsystem.

2.3.3 Data Acquisition Subsystem

The Data Acquisition Subsystem is subdivided into four modules, namely:

- Modular Operating Platform
- Measurement Module
- Control Module
- Interfaces Module

A breakdown of constituent module roles, requirements and realisation progress to date is presented further in this report.

Modular operating platform (A)

The Modular Operating Platform (A) is the physical apparatus providing the SIR system structure and operability through electromechanical functionalities. As previously identified, the developed SIR system must address key challenges (i) and (ii) (listed in the introduction of Subsection 2.3), which emphasises the sheer verticality of lock wall contact surfaces and efficient automation, to ensure effective data acquisition.

The bespoke Mechanical Super-structure (A.3) proposed for the SIR system will address challenge (i). Resembling a large XY Plotter, the structure comprises a rigid vertical metal framework standing parallel to the lock wall, containing a motorised drive mechanism to advance the radar measurement antenna steadily across the survey quadrant, while maintaining a fixed lift-off from the contact surface, sufficiently high to circumvent potential collision with the undulating wall face, but sufficiently low to minimise energy loss and in turn yield clearer subsurface imagery. The mechanism for the super-structure to be supported

by the lock wall is still in development, but it should remain readily detachable to enable efficient repositioning of the survey quadrant as the inspection advances.

The super-structure (A.3) houses the automated Positioning Unit (A.2), which consists of:

A drive mechanism to advance the SIR measurement antenna across the survey quadrant;

Extremal tracking detectors in the form of mechanical microswitches to inform the control system to stop and redirect the antenna at the edges of the traversable survey quadrant and orientation detectors;

A secondary set of limit switches that move with the antenna and serve as orientation sensors and feedback the current orientation of the antenna to the control system to flag to the user, reminding the user to re-orientate the antenna as scanning trajectories switch halfway through the quadrant scan from horizontally advancing to vertically advancing.

Figure 19 shows the final solution for the Positioning Unit (A.2), which uses 1000ppr rotary encoders equivalent to the OMRON E6B2-CWZ6C, and Figure 19 shows the encoder OMRON E6B2-CWZ6C that was used for laboratory testing.

The drive mechanism utilises lead screws connected to two closed loop NEMA34 12NM stepper motors to lineally advance the SIR measurement antenna in x and z independently, with consistent millimetre precision. The closed loop positioning feedback, shown in Figure 19a, exploits rotary encodes of 1000 pulse per revolution (ppr) integrated into the motors and read by the CL86T stepper motor controllers. In laboratory experimentation, the independent OMRON E6B2-CWZ6C 1000ppr encoder shown in Figure 19b was used and connected to a Raspberry Pi to directly export the pulse count (and therefore local coordinates) of what would become movement of the Positioning Unit (A.2).

Figure 19 The Positioning Unit (A.2). (a) final variant; (b) encoder used for laboratory testing

It should be noted that with the CL86T, any discrepancy associated with slip is automatically rectified by the closed-loop feedback system, reducing control system processing demand. The closed loop system can also be utilised to track antenna position relative to the local survey quadrant origin, therein feeding back local coordinate datasets to accompany SIR measurements and inform 3D visualisation of subsurface features. The process is a form of “dead-reckoning” and is crucial to ensuring reliable position data feedback is maintained as the antenna descends further into the lock, progressively diminishing GNSS signal strength (and, in turn, positioning accuracy).

The Modular Operating Platform (A) also includes the Power Unit (A.1) and electrical housings for the onboard electrical systems which enable the measurement and control equipment to function. The main design is based on assumption that mains power provision is available at all prospective inspection sites. However, contingencies for a primary Power Unit (A.1) utilising a rechargeable battery array are being considered, with the option for a battery bypass input to enable the apparatus to be directly run of mains electric, if available onsite. Under current design plans, to power all constitute electrical systems, the Power Unit (A.1) will supply:

- (P1) UK/EU mains 220-249V 50Hz AC power;
- (P2) 48VDC@10A;
- (P3)12VDC@3A, and
- (P4) 5VDC@3A.

Draw from P1 will power the radar controller and slave PC within the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2). Draw from P2 will feed the stepper motor controllers and stepper motors in the Positioning Unit (A.2). Draw from P3 will drive the 4G WIFI Router responsible for delivering RTK GNSS in the Geolocation Unit (B.1). Lastly, P4 will drive the low consumption Raspberry Pi, which forms the Central Interface of the Control Module. Elements features in the architecture diagrams not listed here are powered passively off a listed element, for example the stepper motors passively draw power from the stepper motor controllers and the RTK GNSS antenna passively draws power over USB from the Small Form Factor (SFF) Slave PC in the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2).

At time of writing, architecture pertaining to the electrical systems design is largely finalised with individual subsystems, all tested in isolation within the laboratory environment or in field trials; these details will be presented in deliverable report D2.3 of the CRISTAL project. The electrical system design is also largely independent of the Mechanical Super-Structure (A.3) design, therein stands to remain unaffected by any adjustments to mechanical design made following current discussions with the infrastructure management body.

Measurement module (B)

The primary datasets serving as input for the visualisation of lock wall subsurface features are generated by the Measurement Module (B). This module consists of the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) and the Geolocation Unit (B.1).

The Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) (Figure 20) comprises a monostatic 1GHz Zond radar antenna, the Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller and a Windows Slave PC running Prism2 measurement capture software, as shown in Figure 20. Prism2 software is responsible for trigger radar antenna measurements

and recording radar backscatter patterns to <.SGY> data files. Prism2 (Radar Systems, Inc., 2023) is the proprietary driver for all radar measurement elements, which were all sourced commercially from Radar Systems Inc. (Latvia).

Figure 20 Impulse radar system, comprising: (a) 1GHz antenna; (b) Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller; (c) Prism2 measurement software

From an operational perspective, the settings for measurement capture are carried out through Prism2, with settings and measurement prompt commands converted to a sequence of excitation pulses by the Radar Controller, which continuously sends and receives such excitation pulses in a two-way feedback loop with the connected Radar Antenna, capturing the subsurface response profile.

From a measurement perspective, the radar acquisition process is summarised in Figure 21. The signal partial backscatter (a) underpins the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) measurements, which are then stacked in parallel to form 2D B-scans (b) from individual A-scan response profiles (c).

The radar measurement system utilises kinematic data acquisition, i.e., the antenna must be advanced linearly across the contact surface of interest whilst taking measurements, as, which shows the overall data acquisition process. The transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) elements within antenna are advanced in a linear trajectory over finite duration $t > 0$, over a subsurface volume containing multiple material media M_i exhibiting differing electrical characteristics. In the example shown in Figure 21, black structures denote subsurface pipe features. The green circle highlights a region of strong back scatter intensity. The localised hyperbola about this peak (marked in yellow) indicates the presence of a subsurface feature of interest. This diagram assumes SIR operation on flat horizontal ground; however, the same measurement principle also applies when the antenna is instead advanced linearly across a vertical lock wall. In that context, the subsurface is the regions directly behind the wall, rather than below the ground.

Figure 21 Radar system data acquisition process

A standalone radar measurement is called an “A-scan”, indicated by the red line in Figure 21b and inset Figure 21c. An “A-scan” measurement is associated with the subsurface response in the local vicinity of a fixed point on the contact surface. The Zond 12e is an “Impulse” radar system, meaning the temporal response of the subsurface is directly recorded as an A-scan is captured. The antenna’s transmitter element directs a pulsed waveform of set duration and amplitude into the subsurface, which partially backscatters from any dielectric gradients within the subsurface (i.e., material interfaces). The antenna’s receiver elements monitor the two-way travel time delay and associated amplitude of returning backscattered waveforms across a predefined listening interval. An A-scan is the resultant plot of return signal amplitude against time, which naturally decays as the excitation signal is progressively absorbed and scattered as the signal propagates through inherently heterogeneous subsurface media.

“B-scans” are 2D transects of the subsurface response profiles, typically formed from parallel stacking of successive A-scans. B-scans are also referred to as subsurface “transects”. They are aligned perpendicular to the contact surface. The recovery of 3D subsurface radar datasets is achieved by collecting multiple B-scans in a 2D grid pattern, in this case across the lock wall survey quadrant. A 3D position coordinate, two-way travel time and return signal amplitude can be assigned to each datapoint, therein creating a SIR point cloud of the survey quadrant volume. This point cloud facilitates the generation of 3D visualisations of features within the subsurface. Further 2D output visuals can also be returned by taking planar slices of the point cloud, in a process known as ‘time-slicing’, as the two-way travel time of the returning signal is parameterised in visual output rendering to achieve this.

The Geolocation Unit (B.1) informs the 3D position coordinates of each recorded datapoint. This simplifies to tracking the location of the antenna centre-point in 3D space as it tracks along the lock wall, given the

penetration depth (r) of each datapoint can be computed from the two-way travel time (t) of individual A-scan measurements by the approximation:

$$r = \frac{vt}{2} = \frac{ct}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_r(x, y, z)}} \approx \frac{ct}{2\sqrt{\hat{\epsilon}_r}} \quad (1)$$

where v is wave propagation velocity through the subsurface, which can be expressed in terms of the speed of light in a vacuum (c) and the relative electrical permittivity of the subsurface medium (ϵ_r). It should be mentioned that ϵ_r is an unknown variable scalar field $\epsilon_r(x, y, z)$ across the extent of the subsurface. For the purposes of this report and estimated time to depth axis conversion in visualisations, a practical approximation is to assume the scalar field remains constant across the subsurface ($\epsilon_r = \hat{\epsilon}_r$). With more advanced processing, it is possible to better approximate the true variable field for a more accurate depth estimation, and this will be refined in further phases of SIR system development.

Global geographic coordinates of Easting (E), Northing (N) and Elevation (H) are calculated from Latitude, Longitude and Elevation data gathered using a zBELL RTK GNSS antenna (shown in Figure 22a), which will be mounted atop the GPR antenna as it tracks along the lock wall. RTK stands for Real-Time Kinematic GNSS, a higher precision version of standard GNSS position tracking, capable of positioning accuracy down to 10mm compared to typical 1m resolution of standard GNSS. The correction process is achieved automatically through an internet connection, allowing the antenna to correct positioning data through update from both satellite and terrestrial base stations. The requirement of an internet connection requires the integration of a TP-Link Archer AC750 4G WIFI Router (shown in Figure 22b) into the SIR Geolocation Unit (B.1), to provide reliable internet access across even remote lock sites on the network.

Figure 22 Geolocation Unit (B.1), comprising: (a) zBELL RTK GNSS antenna; (b) TP-Link Archer AC750 4G WIFI Router

The global coordinates facilitate the alignment of captured point clouds with other geolocated datasets gathered by the infrastructure manager during the eventual digitalisation and integration of the wider inland waterways network (e.g., maps of waterway routes, waterside utility assets, vessel position data, etc.) into future iterations of the digital twin. However, geographic coordinates are unsuitable for memory efficient calculations for 3D visualisations owing to the order of integers involved (approaching 10^6 m for measurements across Europe). This requires the concurrent acquisition of local datapoint coordinates relative to the origin of the survey quadrant.

Local coordinates are captured by extracting data from the odometers integrated into the closed loop stepper motors, at $N = 1000$ pulses per revolution, the number of recorded pulses (n) corresponds to an advance by linear distance:

$$S = \left(\frac{n}{N}\right)P \quad (2)$$

where P denotes the pitch of the leadscrews in metres. This data will be directly fed to the control subsystem and integrated with radar measurement and global geolocation data during synchronisation to the Local Data Storage Unit.

Control module (C)

All processes for the SIR system are regulated by the Central Interface, which is provided by a Raspberry Pi. The primary role of the Central Interface is to coordinate the order of operations executed by the Data Acquisition Subsystem. This reduces the complexity of the network of electromechanical element communications to a single script, simplifying the debugging process. The order of operations will always follow: (i) input; (ii) movement; and (iii) measurement. This ensures the end-users commands are always acted upon first and prioritises emergency stopping of the apparatus. The cycle repeats throughout the duration of a quadrant survey. The secondary role of the Central Interface is as a local server, to facilitate data transfer across the Data Acquisition Subsystem and Data Management Subsystem, respectively. The Raspberry Pi runs a local network server designated as “hot store”. This is the local repository for raw measurement data recovered by the Measurement Module (B). The server allows raw data to be pulled to local commercial-grade PC(s) to undergo Data Analytics operations, which are further described in Subsection 0. At all stages of the Data Analytics module process chain, updated version of SIR data can be synchronised with the hot store. A copy of the raw measurement data is always preserved on the hot store, mitigating the risk of inadvertent data overwrite during synchronisation. In early design phases, use of a microcontroller such as the Arduino Uno or ESP32 had been considered for the Central Interface. Also, in an alternate approach, the roles of the SFF Slave PC and Central Interface would have been combined and shared within a single SFF desktop PC. Ultimately, these approaches were abandoned in favour of using a Raspberry Pi as the Central Interface. The SFF desktop PC strategy was complicated by a lack of integrated GPIO connectivity interfaces for communication with the Positioning Unit (A.2). Whilst both microcontrollers and the Raspberry Pi support the multiple required interfaces (e.g., LAN, GPIO, DSI and WIFI) to communicate with all elements of the Data Acquisition Subsystem, the Raspberry Pi was favoured due to its more versatile high-level python-based programming functionality, which offered greater development potential, especially for the essential end-user GUI. The use of Python could also be

subsequently exploited in development of the Data Management Subsystem, as Python also offers competitive functionality for simulation, data processing and data visualisation.

Interfaces Module (D)

Local control is facilitated through a 7 Inch Touchscreen Module for Raspberry Pi, connected to the Central Interface via a miniature DSI ribbon cable. A water-resistant seal was created between the touchscreen module and electrical housing using silicone sealant for outdoor deployment. The screen is mounted directly above mechanical pushbutton controls to stop, run, manoeuvre and home the Modular Operating Platform (A) carriage. These buttons serve as a tactile interface, and contingency in the event of damage to the touchscreen. Remote control is facilitated over local WIFI between the Raspberry Pi and host tablet device. A dedicated application will allow the operator full control over carriage movement (both manual and automatic) and scan parameter configuration. Options will also exist to restart a quadrant scan from a specific B-scan measurement, in the event a quadrant scan was terminated midway through (e.g. by survey scheduling changes). The same GUI will be displayed on both the local and remote interfaces; however, the local interface will be locked out when the remote interface is in use to prevent duplication of commands or unwanted command input. The screen display of system status and measurement data will continue to update on the local interface; however, user input options will be disabled. Also, the physical emergency stop button will continue to work irrespective of local or remote-control operation. In the event this is pressed, a warning will be displayed across all GUIs to notify all operators of the situation. Control to terminate or resume the current quadrant scan will defer to the remote interface (if enabled). Connection between the remote interface and Central Interface should be always maintained to enable continuous system feedback to the operator. However, in the case of signal drop out or other connection related issues, control will defer to the local interface. The system will continue to attempt to reconnect to the remote interface for the remaining duration of the outstanding scan runtime until either the scan completes or connection to the remote interface is restored. In the event connection is restored, the local interface will again automatically lock out.

2.3.4 Data Management Subsystem

The Data Management Subsystem consists of the Local Data Storage Module (E), Data Analytics Module (F) and Data Transfer Module (G). This subsystem is responsible for the conversion of raw SIR measurement data into more intuitive visualisations to be shared with the end user, alongside the consolidation of key metadata to contextualise both the individual quadrant surveys and individual subsurface features identified within the associated data volumes.

During data acquisition, measurement data is passed to the Local Data Storage Module (E). The module comprises physically of cold store media, principally in the form of a USB stick or external memory card connected to the Central Interface. In this context, the term “cold” denotes physical storage, which can be regarded as any format of data storage media that does not require a continuous supply of power.

The Central Interface runs <samba>, allowing it to function as a local network server, serving as a repository for wireless data transfer. As the Central Interface must be powered on for the server to be accessed remotely, it is designated the “hot store”. During data acquisition, for computational and runtime efficiency, individual B-scans are saved locally to the internal memory of the Central Interface. As the carriage repositions between B-scan measurements, the Central Interface will first copy the local files

to the cold store, then upload the files to the hot store. The Central Interface will keep a copy of all measured files on its local internal memory, cyclically overwriting the oldest files once the internal memory usage reaches a designated level (to be formalised during physical system testing). It is expected that repositioning of the carriage will take between 1-5 seconds, providing sufficient time to export data files to the cold store. However, this may prove not long enough to also synchronise files with the hot store. Ideally, file synchronisation will be run concurrently with data acquisition execution; however, should this not be possible without noticeable impact on data acquisition runtime the next best course of action would be to synchronise all data files for the complete quadrant scan to the hot store at the end of the quadrant scan. The specific approach will require hands on interaction with the future prototype SIR system. The Data Analytics Module (F) has the role to convert raw measurement data to human interpretable visuals, principally as 3D objects with supporting visual exports in 2D for the benefit of reports, documentation, cross-checking with conventional handheld radar system output, etc. An overview of the workflow has been detailed in Figure 23 with key processes highlighted. A dedicated series of programs are currently being developed, to return 3D visualisations of features within SIR data.

Figure 23 Workflow for SIR system Data Analytics Module (F)

As an outline, input data in the form of physical or simulated B-scan measurements, local and global geolocation data and metadata informing survey design is passed to the Data Analytics Module (F). The first stage is data processing, where datasets are cleaned and enriched through algorithms such as time variable gain adjustment, migration, and combined processing methodology in order to improve the

clarity and prevalence of features within measurement data from the background noise and “clutter” inherently captured in real environments.

3D visualisation next takes the raw B-scan measurements and geolocation data, merges the datasets to form a point cloud of the survey quadrant volume, interpolates the resultant field to predict the response profiles of the space between measurements then generates Isosurfaces of the resultant response field (akin to medical imaging in CT and MRI scans) to visualise concealed features as 3D objects. 2D visuals can subsequently be generated by fixing isovalues associated with specific coordinate planes or generating projections of 3D objects from specific viewing angles.

The final stage is Feature Classification, where labels predicting the type of material associated with each feature are assigned with associated confidence intervals to help end users make informed decisions about the nature of features observed (note the final decision on the nature of an identified feature is made by the end user, not the SIR system itself). At time of writing, development of the feature classification workflow awaits the completion and refinement of the 3D visualisation workflow.

The final module in the Data Management Subsystem is the Data Transfer Module (G). In this module, following the execution of Data Analytics, processed data is synchronised back into the hot store alongside the original raw data. From here, metadata concerning individual 3D features and the survey itself, alongside the output 3D and 2D visualisations are transferred to the end user, be this directly or through the Digital Twin.

2.3.5 Structure of SIR Datasets

Data associated with the SIR system is divided into two sets, as follows:

- Required dataset (DS1): This dataset comprises any input data required prior to the undertaking of a practical SIR inspection of a waterway’s infrastructure asset for the system to be considered in a fully operable state. This includes all necessary information required to appropriately plan, document and record inspections prior to onsite activities, encompassing prerequisite data inputs listed in Figure 17. Such data would be supplied by the relevant infrastructure management organisation in the form of technical documentation.
- Return dataset (DS2): This includes any output data from the SIR system up to the Data Transfer Module (G). This dataset can be further subdivided in two. First, intermediary output data used locally within the SIR system (DS2.1) and internally synchronised between the cold and hot storage elements in the Local Data Storage Module (E) to be passed through the Data Analytics Module (F); this data is not required for external synchronisation with the digital twin via the Data Transfer Module (G). Second, finalised output data from the Data Analytics Module (F), which is synchronised both internally within the Local Data Storage Module (E) and externally to the digital twin via the Data Transfer Module (G).

The data structure for DS1 and DS2 has been analysed and defined in detail within WP5. A detailed specification has been developed for each item for each associated data field in DS1 and DS2 respectively.

As a brief outline, prospective prerequisite data identified for DS1 include:

- A unique identifier for the infrastructure being inspected;
- A unique location identifier for the infrastructure being inspected;
- A brief of formal inspection requirements, including specific aims and objectives;
- The date and time of scheduled inspection;
- Technical specifications of the infrastructure undergoing inspection (e.g., lock wall dimensions, structural age, any access obstructions, etc.);
- A summary of onsite facilities (i.e., power access, plant machinery, safety equipment, etc.);
- Any additional information regarding logistics necessary for the inspection (e.g., relevant maintenance plans, events, and history; access arrangements and timescales; etc.).

Prospective data identified for DS2 includes:

- Survey quadrant metadata, including, but not limited to, unique and diagrammed identifiers for the lock and localised survey quadrants within the lock;
- Survey feature data, including, but not limited to, vectorised 2D and 3D image/video-based visualisations of subsurface geometry;
- Survey feature metadata, including, but not limited to, feature centroid locations, size/volume estimates and material classifier(s).

Further details concerning SIR datasets will be included in deliverable D5.2 “Data integration and data model”.

2.3.6 Preliminary Testing and Proof-of-Concept

This section presents experimental activities undertaken to explore and demonstrate the viability of the proposed SIR subsystems, modules, and units. The proof-of-concept tests conducted to date have validated the expected capabilities of SIR system constituents, as these were designed and/or selected to fulfil different functionalities, so that the overall system will effectively capture and deliver informative results for end users.

2.3.7 Measurement Control and Automation

Proof-of-concept testing for control and automation of the SIR system comprised two different types of tests:

- Testing of measurement position automation
- Testing of measurement triggering automation.

These tests required development and use of specific rigs and experimental set-ups that have been designed for this scope. The objective was to assess the capabilities of the radar system for being controlled and automated, which are essential features for the considered application (i.e., inspection of lock structure, which comprises two walls of large areas). The experimental set-ups and detailed testing procedures are presented in Appendix II.

2.3.8 RTK GNSS Geolocation Recovery

Configuration and interfacing of the Geolocation Unit (B.1) and Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) required preliminary testing of hardware setup and network connections between the zBELL RTK GNSS geolocation antenna and Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller to ensure effective communication between both elements during data acquisition. Testing procedures and results are presented in detail in Appendix II.

2.3.9 Performance Appraisal of Concrete Inspection Radar System (Proceq GP8000)

To inform radar system selection, interface design and the current state of the art in concrete subsurface inspection, a Proceq GP8000 handheld inspection system from SURVEYTECH, as pictured in Figure 24, was hired. The tool was used to perform preliminary scanning of an in-service lock chamber wall to provide further information on the expected composition of a healthy wall structure. Further details of this fieldwork will be provided in D2.3.

Figure 24 Proceq GP8000 SFCW handheld radar system for concrete structure subsurface inspection (Allied Associates Geophysical, 2024)

For the purposes of D2.2, hands-on interaction with the Proceq GP8000 in the laboratory environment granted insight into the performance capabilities in the context of lock wall subsurface inspection, which have since informed design of the SIR system itself.

Firstly, the area scan measurement procedure of the SFCW system was observed first-hand. Constituent full B-scan measurements across 1m took between 10-30 seconds to complete. Whilst this was considerably faster than the direct application of the SFCW system from rail tunnel inspection, it was the reset and transfer delay of 10-20 seconds between each B-scan which incurred difficulties. With one operator controlling the handheld movement and the other controlling the acquisition of measurement data using a tablet, on numerous occasions full B-scans had to be redone due to one operator starting too soon or too late.

The main observation, and principal reason why the Zond 12e system was selected over any attempts to augment a Proceq GP8000, was surface contact clearance and measurement triggering. The Proceq GP8000 is designed to operate with a ground clearance of 8mm. Concrete walls of the lock chamber can undulate by upwards of 10-20mm, resulting in a loss of contact between the handheld unit's wheels and the contact surface. The wheels house the rotary encoders which inform the GP8000 the system that it has advanced and to begin the next measurement. As a result, frequently measurements would stall as the Proceq GP8000 was advanced, which could easily be missed by the operators resulting in skewed output visuals. These issues were exacerbated if the operator switched from using their hand to using the rigid boom extender to move the Proceq GP8000. If the unit encountered undulation with the boom, the Proceq GP8000 abruptly stopped moving and jammed. If movement was achieved with the equally rigid SIR system Positioning Unit (A.2), such a jam would have either damaged the measurement antenna, motors or in a worst case the lock wall. Therefore, these observations were key motivators for adoption of the Zond Impulse Radar system over the Proceq GP8000 for the SIR system.

Finally, interaction with the Proceq GP8000 inspired the integration of the RC-Interface and Isosurface visualisation approaches in the development of the SIR system. The Proceq GP8000's IOS application provides the end user with a visual representation of the area scan trajectories, highlighting the current positioning and movement path of the antenna at any given instant. The clarity of this functionality for end user interaction was noted and has inspired adoption of a similar approach in design drafting for an RC-Interface GUI for the SIR system (see Section 2.3.2.1) with the addition of options for movement controls.

2.3.10 Developing Tools for SIR 3D Visualisation Workflow

Developing Bespoke Area Scan Simulation Toolkit for Upcoming 3D Visualisation

A reoccurring challenge was the lack of technical details which can be provided about the true state of infrastructure scanned by the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) as a reference or benchmark to compare the scan data against. In developing a bespoke workflow to return accurate 2D and 3D visualisations of subsurface features for the SIR system, the accuracy of the returned visuals must be robustly validated. This validation procedure can be achieved in one of two ways.

Firstly, the more direct physical approach is to scan of a typical lock wall structure (or lock wall structure analogue) in an arbitrary state. A subsurface feature can be subsequently introduced in the physical world, the system can be re-scanned and the difference between the two datasets returned enables a reconstruction of the feature and provides a comparison for accuracy. This approach proves impractical on multiple fronts, critically in that defects should not be deliberately introduced into healthy lock wall structures, nor can the introduced features be sufficiently accurately measured on site to provide a scaled basis for comparative reference (i.e., a "ground truth").

The second approach would be to simulate radar measurements of virtual features within virtual structures, which is considered the more viable strategy, as the exact locations of each programmed feature can be exported with absolute precision to provide ground truth datasets. As well as providing radar measurements to test the developing 3D visualisation workflow, these simulations can also examine the impact of rebar placement within the lock chamber walls on expected quality of visualisation output.

This is important given the uncertainty at the time concerning the anticipated depth of the first rebar layers in a typical lock structure, based on discussions with the infrastructure managers to date.

gprMax is a leading open-source simulation toolkit for radar measurement simulation (Warren et al., 2016). The programme is python-based and supports the integration of custom-scripting. This proved invaluable for simulating area scan measurements of lock wall substructures, as whilst the base program was designed to simulate individual B-scans, a dedicated tool for area scanning - as in the case of a lock wall quadrant scan – required bespoke development. Key illustrations of the simulation process developed are shown in Figure 25.

The developed procedure creates a 3D ground truth test geometry, which is defined programmatically in python and can be subsequently previewed in the external application Paraview. Note for the purpose of simulation, a vertical concrete wall quadrant can be considered equivalent to a horizontal concrete ground quadrant. A 2D grid of perpendicular B-scan trajectories is next automatically defined and previewed before successive B-scan measurements are simulated sequentially in gprMax across the full quadrant. Note the choice of an intersecting grid pattern is essential for recovering 3D visualisations of subsurface features.

Figure 25 Bespoke quadrant scan simulation in gprMax previews ground-truth geometry (a) and scanning trajectories (b)

Furthermore, geometry positioning and alignment in the base programme was by default based off the lower left vertex of the simulation domain. This made the design of simulation geometry highly involved and prone to calculation error, owing to the required offsets between target features and the PML boundary of the simulation space, alongside the essential airgap at the top of the simulation for antenna placement to be well defined. Therefore, in designing a bespoke tool for area scanning, a bespoke coordinate transform, termed “Centre-Aligned Subsurface Geometry” (CASG), had to be developed and integrated into the programme to redefine a more intuitive geometry placement based off the origin of the subsurface region of interest.

As illustrated in Figure 26, the antenna is modelled by individual transmitter (red) and receiver elements (blue). The position of the antenna at any point in time is defined by the midpoint of the element centres, connected by the orientation vector γ .

Figure 26 Centre Aligned Subsurface Geometry (CASG) coordinate transform defines a bistatic antenna

The gprMax default 3D simulation domain is illustrated in Figure 27. Note the requisite inclusion of an air gap at the top of the domain and definition of the origin at the lower left vertex of the simulation domain. In practice, highly involved manual calculations and scale drawings are required to calculate positioning coordinates of simulation bodies such as the antenna or defects whilst programming a simulation, a slow process susceptible to human-error.

Figure 27 Illustration of the 3D domain of a typical gprMax simulation

In defining the CASG coordinate transform illustrated in Figure 28 the simulation volume is defined with features occupying a central cuboidal region of interest (brown) surrounded by a buffer region in which antenna initial placement is defined. This choice ensures the antenna always tracks across the entirety of the region of interest during a simulation, maximising the coverage of a quadrant area scan. The outermost region of the simulation domain is occupied by the Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) boundary, which emulates the effect of an infinite domain in all directions, therein mitigating the interference of electromagnetic artefacts associated with a finite simulation domain. Importantly, the CASG coordinate transform maps the origin of the simulation from the lower left vertex to the centre of the subsurface region of interest. This introduces positioning symmetry to simplify the programming of bodies within the simulation, allowing geometry declaration to be more readily automated without dependency on highly involved human-led computation or over-reliance on scale drawings.

Further development currently in progress is the 3D visualisation workflow in python, for which the gprMax CASG tester geometry illustrated in Figure 29 forms the basis of visualisation testing. This is a Paraview preview for an area scan of a metallic sphere and two metallic pipes within a homogeneous concrete domain. Note the opacity of the concrete media has been reduced for clarity of the geometry present.

Figure 28 illustration of CASG coordinate transform with origin mapped to the centre of the subsurface region of interest.

Figure 29 Paraview preview of gprMax CASG generated tester geometry for 3D visualisation development

Interfacing Prism2 & gprMax To GPRPy Data Processing Platform

Pre-processing of raw SIR datasets prior to 3D visualisation suppresses noise in observed measurements and in turn enriches the clarity of features of interest within the subsurface. The Pre-Processing module will utilise the open-source toolkit GPRPy (Plattner, 2020) to facilitate core pre-processing operations of:

- DeWow: Low-cut filter suppressing noise artifacts in each A-scan independently.
- Gain Adjustment: Time variable amplification of collective A-scan signal amplitudes.
- Background Subtraction: Suppression of common noise artifacts across a full B-scan.
- Smoothing: A-scans are oversampled and updated with windowed moving average.
- f/k -Migration: Phase-shift corrections compensate for measurement distortions.

More advanced data pre-processing techniques (e.g., Combined Processing Methodology) will be applied using bespoke python scripts, either integrated into the GPRPy toolkit or running standalone in the process chain following data export from GPRPy.

Multiple challenges were encountered in establishing the order of operations and the integration of GPRPy to the Data Analytics Module (F). First the conversion of B-scan measurement data from Prism2's associated <.SGY> binary data format to the MALA binary <.rd7> main data files and <.rad> header files recognised by GPRPy. In preliminary tests of data export, ASCII <.txt> exports of B-scan amplitude data and global position coordinates were achieved using the integrated exporter format options within Prism2 itself. Currently, this requires each B-scan to be sequentially opened in Prism2 and exported through GUI interaction. In further developments, this procedure will be replaced with a dedicated python script to perform <.SGY> à <.txt> à <.rad/.rd7> conversion more efficiently.

Communication with Radar Systems Inc. has returned documentation of the <.SGY> binary file structure which will inform design of this script. For maximal tractability and versatility of data recovered, wherever possible data will be converted to human-readable <.txt> format wherever more obscure specialist data formats are required for program compatibility or functional efficiency.

GPRPy requires dual file input to import B-scans. This includes a <.rad> ASCII header file containing metadata associated with a radar survey and a <.rd7> binary data file (little endian format) containing the measurement data as a continuous binary string sequenced radar sample by sample for each A-scan sequentially. It was initially observed <.rad> files required 38 independent metadata field entries ranging from expected fields such as “sample count” and “distance interval” to MALA specialist fields such as “system calibration” metrics and “fixing” flags, data unavailable from the metadata files associated with the Zond Impulse radar system. Communication with technical advisors from MALA, deconstruction of the GPRPy source code and a practical trail deleting fields line by line from a sample <.rad> file (checking the file continued to import to GPRPy successfully) identified only three critical fields required population: (i) A-scan sample count; (ii) A-scan separation distance increment and (iii) A-scan measurement time window. These observations allowed the SIR team to design bespoke conversion scripts to return the <.rad> a <.rd7> files respectively associated with an input <.txt> recovered from Prism2.

By extension, gprMax simulation output takes the form of <.out> files, which upon inspection are specialisations of the more generic <.hdf5> data storage format. Again, to facilitate data import to GPRPy for pre-processing, conversion from <.hdf5> à <.txt> à <.rad/.rd7> was required. The previous <.rad> and <.rd7> generator scripts could be reused here. Conversion from <.hdf5> to <.txt> was achieved using the <h5py> module to extract data stored under the <.hdf5> file’s receiver data path. This process was sequentially called iterating the B-scan identified index to cycle through and convert all B-scans associated with a specific area scan.

To validate conversion accuracy, side by side visual comparisons were carried out of output data from gprMax displayed using the programs inbuilt plotter command against the GPRPy import preview. An initial discrepancy was observed wherein the import introduced distortions to the GPRPy import. In the case of the “hello-world” example provided in the gprMax documentation, the expected standalone hyperbola was observed to be absent, replaced by an image containing what appeared to be exclusively noise. This was debugged and the cause of the discrepancy was determined as being a difference between the orientation of B-scan data arrays for gprMax and GPRPy respectively. Where gprMax exports map the sample index of datapoints in each A-scan to the rows of the output array, with the A-scan index assigned to the columns, GPRPy expects the transpose of this matrix as input. Introduction of the transpose operation rectified the observed discrepancy, yielding the agreement between gprMax export and GPRPy import observed in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Bespoke conversion scripts successfully convert gprMax <.hdf5> output files to GPRPy <.rad/.rd7> input files

2.3.11 3D Isosurface Generation on Test Geometries

As detailed in Figure 23, a workflow is being developed to return 3D visualisations of subsurface features within recorded quadrant volume datasets. Taking inspiration from medical imaging and discussion with the developers of both gprMax and GPRPy, work is underway to extract 3D Isosurfaces from the point cloud defined by the scalar field:

$$F = F([x, y, z], t, B, \dots) \quad (3)$$

Where $[x, y, z]$ denote the 3D local coordinates of an individual datapoint relative to the local origin of the specific quadrant measured (i.e., a standalone sample from a radar A-scan measurement), t denotes the recorded two-way travel time between initial excitation signal transmission and receiver measurement of the datapoint and B denotes the observed temporal response amplitude of the radar measurement recorded. The point cloud is currently stored as a <polyData> object using the <PyVista> module for 3D visualisation and <.VTK> file manipulation in python. This point cloud will eventually contain further data fields associated with visualisation parameters such as opacity and data point RGB colouration, alongside secondary measurement data compute from the measured response profiles, an example would include the frequency response profiles.

Recovery of Isosurfaces requires the raw point cloud to undergo 3D interpolation to populate the response profile of 3D regions of space between observed measurements. Further developments will involve analysis of the performance of interpolation based on Nearest Neighbour, Trilinear, Cubic, Radial Basis Function and Kriging. In current development, 3D Isosurface generation will be achieved using the “Flying Edges” algorithm. An Isosurface is defined to be any region of the 3D scalar field which has an amplitude equal to a globally defined isovalue parameter. Varying the isovalue updates the specific Isosurface generated as illustrated in the Barth Sextic example in Figure 31 (PyVista, 2023). This visual is generated to demonstrate the python <PyVista> module “flying edges” Isosurface reconstruction tool. The isovalue for which the Isosurface is generated is reduced moving from render (a) to render (b). In an authentic SIR dataset containing noise and more complex geometry, the Isosurfaces generated are

expected to exhibit a more discontinuous appearance, however the premise of Isosurface generation being performed remains equivalent to this demonstration.

Figure 31 Demonstration of Isosurface generation on a Barth Sextic scalar field for differing isovalues in (a) and (b)

In the context of a medical scan, this isovalue can be naturally associated with the density of the material medium being imaged (e.g. lower density skin vs higher density bone). In the context of SIR datasets, the isovalue denotes regions of the radar response profile of comparable magnitude, which can be influenced not only by material density, but also depth, shape and form (i.e., similar electromagnetic properties, consistent often with features of similar physical characteristics) This further highlights the importance of the pre-processing module, which seeks to standardise response profiles therein making comparisons of signal magnitude and feature contents more physically meaningful.

Considering further development work related to the export of 2D visualisations from 3D Isosurfaces, multiple routes are available. Firstly, time slicing, where in the 2D magnitude of the response field B is exported for a set two way travel time t . Equally, 2D spatial slices of the resultant 3D Isosurfaces could also be returned by mapping the isovalue to one of the spatial coordinates x , y or z respectively. Projection mappings would also be possible, effectively imaging the shadow of the 3D Isosurfaces cast on either the XY , XZ or YZ plane. This would be useful for conveying the form of 3D structures in physical reports (on 2D paper) and conveying the relative locations of 3D features within a quadrant volume when the scanning environment contains a dense collection of features (e.g. in the presence of one or more void-washout defects).

2.3.12 Implementation of SIR Prototype

The concept design of the SIR system is multifaceted, taking into consideration the necessary functionalities of the system and practical options for physical system configuration approaches, capabilities, and restrictions. Aspects that needed to be considered include the deployment environment and its specific regulations, including both for the physical inspection environment itself and the end-user(s). Safety requirements and considerations for best-working practice were highly influential in the design of the SIR system. A refined concept design of the SIR system is presented in Figure 32, which

enables completion of straight-line scanning trajectories forming a 2D grid balances data acquisition runtime against quality of returned data.

Figure 32 Refined concept design of the SIR system (example installation on a generic empty lock)

The Mechanical Super-structure (A.3) spans a localised survey quadrant on the lock wall. The Positioning Unit (A.2) advances a carriage across the quadrant, along individual linear B-scans sequentially during data acquisition in a serpentine curve scanning trajectory.

For operational reasons, the SIR system was designed to track the radar antenna across the lock wall in two sequential serpentine curve trajectories shown in Figure 33. The trajectories gather a 2D grid of intersecting B-scans to form the subsurface radar point cloud required for feature 3D visualisation. The serpentine curves are offset by 90 degrees. In the first trajectory, antenna tracking records the grid's horizontal B-scans. In the second trajectory, antenna tracking records the grid's vertical B-scans. Placement of the origin is in the top left corner of the survey quadrant, with advance along trajectories always away from the origin towards the lower right corner of the survey quadrant.

Figure 33 Serpentine curve scanning trajectory comprised of horizontal (yellow arrows) and vertical (white arrows) B-scans

The selection of the continuous serpentine curve instead of a discontinuous sequence of straight-line trajectories was made to maximise the runtime efficiency of the SIR system. The serpentine curve circumvents delays associated with resetting the position of the antenna, which would be necessary in the discontinuous scenario during transition from one trajectory to the next. The serpentine scenario never needs only to reset the location of the antenna, as by completion of the second trajectory the antenna has returned to the origin. The only additional requirement for the serpentine trajectory scenario is to ensure alternate B-scans are reversed to emulate consistent direction of antenna advance, which avoids introducing unwanted distortion artifacts to resultant visualisations.

The carriage houses the Radar Antenna and zBELL RTK GNSS Antenna. All other elements of the Measurement Module (B) do not need to track with the carriage and are permanently situated in an electrical housing attached to the lower left of the super-structure, connected to the carriage by an electrical umbilical cable. The electrical housing also contains the Control Module (C) and Embedded GUI, alongside providing the network connection access for the RC-Interface, linked to a dedicated application on the operator's tablet PC.

Subject to further design refinement, the Power Unit (A.1) will either be housed as illustrated in a standalone housing to the superstructure or will be integrated into the electrical housing on the superstructure. The electrical housing is situated at the base of the Mechanical Super-Structure (A.3) to allow users to interact with the system whilst being safely separated from the space swept by the carriage. Due to restrictions associated with working at height, this cannot be physically located at the top of the super-structure. Integrating the RC-Interface extends the zone of interaction to beyond the confines of the lock chamber. Potentially, an operator could reasonably operate and oversee the apparatus from the safe set-back distance atop the opposite lock wall.

To ensure safe shutdown in the event of any system issues, a physical emergency stop button will be mounted on the electrical control box directly below the touchscreen to halt the probe and allow operators to safely perform system diagnostics. There will also be a digital emergency stop button on the RC-Interface, which will always be displayed whenever quadrant scanning is in progress. All scanning operations and safety procedures centrally managed by the Control Module (C). In the unlikely event of power interruption, all electromechanical systems cease by default, mitigating unanticipated motion of the carriage, ensuring the safety of equipment and operators. Measurement data is saved immediately upon completion of each individual B-scan, therefore partially completed quadrant scans can be readily resumed, with minimal risk of data corruption.

The concept design of the super-structure and its constituent electromechanical elements minimises the weight and bulk of the physical apparatus to maximise system portability without compromising system integrity or stability. This will facilitate effective repositioning of the Modular Operating Platform (A) to subsequent scanning quadrants.

2.4. CRISTAL Acoustic Emission (AE) System

2.4.1 AE System Realization

Acoustic Emission (AE) is a powerful non-destructive testing technique used for monitoring structural integrity, detecting flaws, and assessing material behaviour under stress. This short overview provides a glimpse into the current state-of-the-art in AE apparatus, covering both laboratory and industrial applications. The heart of any AE system is its sensor. Modern AE sensors are highly sensitive, capable of detecting ultrasonic waves generated by microstructural changes or crack propagation. Piezoelectric are the most widely used for their excellent sensitivity and bandwidth.

Advancements in signal processing have greatly enhanced the capability to distinguish relevant AE signals from noise. Digital signal processing techniques, including wavelet analysis and machine learning algorithms, contribute to improved signal-to-noise ratios and more accurate event classification. In the industrial sector, AE plays a crucial role in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). Automated AE systems continuously monitor structures like bridges, pipelines, and aircraft for signs of degradation or impending failure. Wireless sensor networks and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have facilitated real-time monitoring.

Recent developments include embedding AE sensors directly into materials, creating 'smart materials' capable of self-monitoring. This innovation is particularly significant in aerospace and automotive industries, where early detection of structural issues is critical. This feature could have a practical approach in future water-lock gate design and manufacturing by embedding AE sensors.

Advancements in machine learning and AI are paving the way for autonomous AE monitoring systems. These systems can learn and adapt to complex structural behaviours, enabling more proactive maintenance and reducing the reliance on manual analysis. AE technology can detect failures in structures that may not be easily observable through conventional visual inspections or other non-destructive testing methods. This is due to the following reasons:

- Sensitivity to Microcracks - AE technology is highly sensitive and can detect the acoustic emissions generated by the microcracking processes within the material, even when these cracks are not visible to the naked eye or are below the detection threshold of other inspection methods.
- Real-Time Monitoring - AE technology provides real-time monitoring of structural integrity, allowing for the detection of crack initiation and propagation as they occur, which may not be feasible with periodic visual inspections or other non-destructive testing methods.
- Localized Detection: AE sensors can be strategically placed to provide from fine to sectional localized detection, making it possible to pinpoint the exact location of crack initiation and growth within a structure, even in areas that are challenging to access or inspect using traditional methods.
- Early Warning of Critical Damage: By detecting the acoustic emissions associated with crack initiation and propagation, AE technology can provide early warning of critical damage that may not be apparent through visual inspections, enabling timely intervention to prevent catastrophic failures.

Figure 34 displays a typical steel made water-lock gate. As can be seen it consists from welded steel sheets and steel beams. The predictive maintenance must be able to detect microcracks over gate's steel structure and also loose pieces of metals on the gate and imminent failures on the piston mechanism providing the required force for the gate to operate. Microcrack in a steel media produces elastic waves travelling through the body of the gate, and the same applies for the any loose metallic parts in impact with the gate itself. Microcracks in steel, generated due to strain or other mechanical stresses, can produce acoustic emissions with a frequency bandwidth typically ranging from a few kilohertz (kHz) to several megahertz (MHz). The exact frequency bandwidth depends on various factors, including the size and geometry of the microcracks, the material properties of the steel, the nature of the applied stress, and the surrounding environmental conditions.

Microcracks in steel can be monitored using various techniques, including mainly acoustic emission (AE). AE monitoring is particularly well-suited for detecting and characterizing microcracks because it directly measures the acoustic signals generated by crack propagation through elastic waves. AE sensors are sensitive to high-frequency acoustic emissions produced by microcrack initiation, growth, and propagation within the material. On the other hand, accelerometers measure the vibrations or accelerations produced by crack activity as the elastic waves hit the media surface and may be useful for detecting larger-scale vibrations associated with medium to large crack. However, AE sensors for the case of predictive maintenance where the detection of very initial weak microcrack signals is required, are the sensors of preference due to its superior sensitivity.

Figure 34 B-scans typical steel water lock-gate

The overall AE system realized for Cristal can be viewed at Figure 35. It must be noted here that, according to the description of the AE system Micro-SHM by MISTRAS Figure 36, whose details were provided in D2.1 and reader is encouraged to reference this deliverable for more information. In short, the system has 4 channels with PZT sensors each one capable of transferring to the central wireless data logger AE data through a rugged cable from 2-30 meters long each. Thereon, it is apparent that the whole gate can be covered by placing the sensors to operationally critical joints. Thereon, the whole water-lock gate can be covered. As can be seen from the Figure 36 on selected water lock gates one or more AE devices able to capture the produced acoustic emission of the door during operation are placed and deployed. The AE logger (Micro-SHM) is portable and with wireless capability. As a power source either a 50watt solar panel can be used or normal AC power passed through a small transformer for security reasons .

Figure 35 Schematic description of the AE apparatus and overall working framework realized for CRISTAL

The captured data are wirelessly transferred to the laptop running the dedicated AE software 'AEWin'; capturing the signals, filtering and timestamping them and exporting them into DTA and CSV format files. A constantly looping python code detects new coming data recording files, and parses them.

Both in Figure 35 but also in Figure 36 an easy graphical overall description of the AE CRISTAL framework, starting from up-left corner the water-lock gate under inspection where the AE system is deployed, with measurements recorded by micro-Mistras AE apparatus, and stored by a nearby wirelessly connected laptop, with the measurements been processed through our dedicated developed python code, including components extraction, slotification, feature extraction and vectorization into "Superpixels", with them been remotely transferred for inference and the results into DB freely available by the Digital Twin. It must be noted here that is order to have the highest degree of data mining tailored specifically for CRISTAL we did not used any ready commercial software but instead we used well established, tested in myriads of scientific papers python libraries like 'PyTorch', 'sklearn' and 'scipy' with all underneath coding develop specifically for CRISTAL.

Figure 36 Graphical overall AE system realized for Cristal

The pre and post processed, decomposing and feature extraction performed are:

- Grouping incoming data based on folder, with each folder corresponding to a separate water-lock gate, also sorting based on timestamp sample measurement, and grouping per sensor (currently used 4 sensors per gate).
- Decomposing each timeseries using Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) techniques. Create a pool with the original timeseries and the produced component timeseries.
- Normalization, bandpass and median filters over the pool of timeseries.
- Denoising using pre-trained autoencoders and wavelets over the produced time series
- Slotify the recorded timeseries according to importance of a variable like: energy variable, risetime and avgtime variables.
- Extract for each timeseries component's slot the following features:
 - Splitting the spectral in nth zones, and on each zone calculate the signal energy
 - On each spectral zone the number and position of peaks

- On each spectral zone the mean amplitude value, the variance and kurtosis
- At the time domain the acoustic features Counts of Hits, Duration of Hits, Average Frequency, Counts to peak, Risetime, Initial Frequency and Reverberation frequency.

At the time domain the statistical momentums of mean value, variance, kurtosis and the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the slot.

The produced features per slot are vectorized as to produce a vector of features per slot. Timely align the feature slots and group them per sensor channel and original parent – components timeseries. These vectors are grouped per nth vectors based on the rule of timely nearest neighbours and produce a larger vector of features called “Superpixel”.

Therefore, from the sea of AE measurements, we arrive to ‘Superpixels’ per water lock gate and sensor channels, which are produced through distillation of the important AE signal features. These ‘Superpixels’ are then stored into the data broker DB storage, which then are forwarded into the digital twin for the Machine Learning models to output a prediction number of failure, or in a similar and equally acceptable scenario of firstly inference the neural net in producing a degree of confidence on upcoming failure outputs; which then is passed through the data broker DB storage to the digital twin for further cognitive interpretation.

The ‘Superpixels’ are grouped over a daily time window into a CSV and these CSVs are inferenced by the Machine Learning (ML) models . The generated confidence/prediction results are transmitted as simple JSON messages. JSON is an industry standard that is used almost for the exchange of data between different parties.

Of course, this is just a crash introduction on models coding we developed and more will be said at deliverable D5.2 were the whole modelling and programming approach will be deployed in full.

2.4.2 AE Proof of Concept

In this sub-section a proof of concept will be provided through an in-vivo experiment in the premises of CERTH. It discusses also the matter of calibration, validation and used experimental setup. Regarding the standardization through the calibration and validation. For the purposes of the proof of concept a laboratory test made prior to the first pilot AE measurements, in large metallic structure within the premises of CERTH campus with the purpose to evaluate the deployability of the system and to calibrate the system by selecting correct parameters for the digital filters HDT and other timings and threshold of the Micro-SHM apparatus.

Acoustic emission (AE) is widely used to monitor phenomena such as the formation and propagation of microcracks. When conducting AE experiments one of the major problems encountered is the uncertainty of the measurements due to factors such as the sensitivity of the sensors. The sensitivity of the sensors affects the signals obtained and consequently the conclusions of the studies.

The solution to these problems is calibration, a critical process that ensures the accuracy and reliability of the results, and secondly validation to make sure that whatever results we get are valid. Both for calibration and validation the method used was Pencil Lead Break (PLB). The pencil lead break (PLB)

method is a widely used and standardized technique for calibrating and validating acoustic emission (AE) systems. Here's a brief overview:

- Function: PLB generates a repeatable and well-defined acoustic emission source with consistent characteristics. This allows for:
 - ✓ Calibration: Establishing a reference point to correlate the measured AE signal with its true source amplitude.
 - ✓ Validation: Verifying the system's performance by ensuring it consistently detects and measures the PLB signal within expected parameters.
- Implementation: A standardized pencil lead of specific size and hardness is broken under controlled conditions (e.g., specific force, distance from sensor).
 - ✓ The resulting acoustic emission is detected by the AE sensor.
 - ✓ The characteristics of the AE signal (e.g., peak amplitude, arrival time) are analyzed and compared to established reference values.
- Benefits: Simplicity and cost-effectiveness: PLB is an easy-to-implement and inexpensive method compared to other calibration techniques.
 - ✓ Repeatability: The standardized procedure ensures consistent results for reliable calibration and validation.
 - ✓ Widely accepted: PLB is a well-established and standardized method (e.g., ASTM E1106) used across various industries for AE system verification.
 - ASTM E1106 - Standard Practice for Primary Calibration of Acoustic Emission Sensors: This standard outlines the procedures for the primary calibration of acoustic emission (AE) sensors using various methods, including the PLB technique. It specifies the requirements for the pencil lead, the test setup, and the data analysis procedures.
 - ASTM E569 - Standard Guide for Acoustic Emission Testing: This guide provides a comprehensive overview of AE testing, including various applications, instrumentation, and data analysis techniques. It also mentions the PLB method as a common practice for sensor calibration and validation.
- Conclusion: The PLB method offers a simple, standardized, and cost-effective approach for calibrating and validating AE systems. While it has limitations in frequency range and material dependence, it remains a valuable technique widely used in various AE applications.

2.4.2.1 Experimental Procedure

The calibration experiments were carried out on a structure consisting of orthogonal metal panels. The dimensions of the metal plates are 15m x 0.5m and their structure is shown in Figure 37 (right). The structure used in the experiments simulates water locks as it has similar structural characteristics and rotation capability of the large metallic structures. Figure 37 (left) shows the structure flat and after rotation.

Figure 37 Large testing metal construction before rotation (right) and after full rotation (left)

For the experiments the Micro-SHM and RAEM1, an AE system which is similar to Micro-SHM but with one sensor, devices of acoustic emission were used (Figure 38). The sensors from the Micro-SHM (Figure 39) and RAEM1 were placed on the central metal plate using gel couplant. The purpose of a couplant is to provide a good acoustic matching conductance between the test material to the piezo-transducer. Magnetic holders were used to hold the sensors to the metallic tested structure. The layout of the sensors on the metal plate is parallel as the level where the sensors are placed is 1.5 m from the bottom of the plate. The two types of sensors, the micro SHM and the RAEM1 system, were placed parallel but on the front and back of the plate respectively.

Figure 38 Placement of AE sensors

Figure 39 Acoustic emission Micro-SHM system

The portable used power source for all calibrations was the the EcoFlow River 2 Max Power Station. The EcoFlow River provided the flexibility to carry out the tests by providing a portable power solution for the Micro-SHM and RAEM1 loggers. The connection of the AE equipment to the EcoFlow River 2 Max Power Station is shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40 Placement of AE sensors' Power charge

The process of data transmission from the Micro-SHM and RAEM1 to the computer is shown below. The connection and transmission of data received by the Micro-SHM is wireless, using a Wi-Fi antenna connected to the computer (Figure 41). Similarly, in RAEM1 the detector sample analyzes and processes the signal, and transmits the data to the PC through Wi-Fi or network cable (Figure 41). Both in Micro-SHM and RAEM1, acoustic emission software displays and processes AE signals to predict structure health.

Figure 41 WiFi data transfer bridging

2.4.3 AE Calibration

The experiments carried out to calibrate and simulate the microcrack and to train the model include:

- Normal operation with natural rotation of the metal plates
- Normal operation with natural rotation of the metal plates and simultaneous application of the Pencil Lead Break (PLB) technique
- Application of PLB technique during natural operation without rotation of metal plates
- Simulation of random noise and impacts on the metal plate that are not microcracks

The use of the PLB technique aims to create acoustic emission signals simulation a micro-crack. From the study conducted by Hsu and Nielsen¹, it has been shown that a 0.5 mm pencil with 2 hardness and a contact angle of 45 degrees can simulate the formation and propagation of microcracks. The acoustic emission produced during both pencil lead break and microcrack formation results from the sudden release of stored elastic energy, which leads to the generation of stress waves that propagate through the material.

Two sets of experiments were conducted using Micro-SHM, studying different frequency values. More specifically, the frequency threshold in the analog filter for the AE piezoelectric type AE sensors was first set at 1 kHz and then at 20 kHz. Usually, the frequencies range from 20 kHz to 1 MHz, and in some cases frequencies below 20 kHz improve the tests. Accordingly, the preamplifier of the AE signal in the experiments was set at 33 for the 60 and 150 kHz sensors and 35 dB for the wide band sensors.

The central plate and its neighboring plates were used for the experiments. More specifically, in Figures 42 and 43 the plates concerning experiment 1, experiment 2 and experiment 3, on which the measurements were carried out, are indicated. The points at which the PLB was applied to all 3 plates

were 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 meters from the base of the metal plate. Additional experiments using PLB were also conducted on the metal beam. The sensors throughout the experiments were mounted on the central plate (Figure 42).

Figure 42 Parallel Alignment of sensors

While conducting the experiments it was found that the sensors do not perceive and therefore do not record the energy released to the neighboring plates (experiment 1, experiment 2, experiment 3) when using the PLB technique. Therefore, it was found that the range of a sensor and the area it covers has a total area of 9 sq. meters. For our purposes due to the fact water-lock gates are constructed by welded steel rods we assume a minimum safe factor of 30%, therefore, 3 square meters of usable very sensitive AE activity capturing with high to noise ratio signals. Of course, this estimation is for microcracks and as a possible pre-failure could be much larger than a microcrack it is a safe to set this as a bottom minimum area of small pre-failure detection in the adjacent sensor neighbor, but safely assuming 10 square meters of detection on medium to large crack detection.

The additional necessity of these calibrations was to finetune on detection of possible micro-vibrations, deformations. It is important to distinguish the above from the formation of cracks or defects during plate rotation or immobility. Similarly, random noises and impacts simulate the change in acoustic emission caused by contact or collision of objects with the plate. These have the effect of causing temporary changes in the acoustic signature of the slab, with no actual crack or permanent change in the structure.

2.4.4 AE Validation

As a first level of validation to validate the ability of the configured system to detect microcracks in other structures, we placed the AE system in other places across the experimental metallic structure and performed simple PLB to detect if the estimated surface is indeed valid and the signal to noise ratio is

indeed as it should be (PLB break in other points across the experimental metallic structure previously described Figure 43). Indeed the signal had a minor fluctuation on the amplitude below 1dB and a signal to noise ratio as the one found during the calibration process

Figure 43 Location of the validation PLB points

As a second experimental setup that was used mainly for validation but is worth simply mentioning here as some also primary calibrations on the AE sensors were also performed, is the gathering on thick metallic steel plates of 0.5 cm and 1cm thickness (Figure 44), similar to ones used in the water-lock metallic gates, of PLB. After calibrating on the threshold and setup of the Micro-SHM internal filters on each channel/sensor several LPB were performed mimicking micro-cracks in a steel plate. The recordings were stored in DTA and CSV file format and later used to train an autoencoder neural network, and on a validation subset of the recorded PLBs the presence and detection of micro-crack as classification from the autoencoder neural network was performed. More will be said and written at D5.2.

Figure 44 Results of the step-by-step load/unload test.

Having setup the hardware filters of the AE Micro-SHM during calibration, and having an indication of the area a sensor on a metallic gate can cover, and therefore knowing how close to gate's critical joints the sensor must be placed, we moved with real pilot demonstrations on May of 2023. By visiting three pilot

sites deploying the aforementioned AE system. The visit was performed as an in-site validation of the AE configuration but also to gather some actual data from true gates.

2.4.4.1 In site Validation and AE Data Acquisition on Italian Pilot Conca Di Baricetta

On June of 2023, CERTH visited firstly the Italian water-lock Conca Di Baricetta Figure 45. Here a very simple and brief description of the visit will be performed as the reason of the visit was primary to feed the python code developed for the water-lock gate some data to validate the whole code. The actual recording gate-site of this water lock can be seen at Figure 46.

Figure 45 Conca Di Baricetta water-lock overview , in red circle the position of the measured gate

Figure 46 Conca Di Baricetta actual gate (top left), the placement of the sensors red squares (bottom left), the Micro-SHM (bottom right).

The sensors were placed by a technical from the water-lock firstly cleaning the point of placement on gate's metallic rod quite thorough, for the sensor to have a clean acoustic path to the underneath metallic path, and of course a gel couplant augmenting the acoustic conductance on that specific point of sensor placement.

The following experiments / validation and recording were performed:

- Several open-close operations of the gates to record the acoustic emissions of normal gate operation.
- Several gate recordings of AEs on short gate operations with sudden stops as an attempt the normal operation of the gate for some reason to fail (a general failure).
- One gate recording of acoustic emissions on the door being slightly open with a 2-5 cm open allowing leakage of water through that small opening.
- Various and multiple PLBs nearby sensors placements validating the good signal reception.

To be more precise on the validation procedure recordings with no gate movement were contacted and the time vs amplitude profile of the incoming signal- noise was taken. During the recordings with gate operation and virtual gate failing (sudden starts and stops) the profile of received AE signals over time were taken and compared with the profile of noise. The number of hits were clearly 2-fold more than the corresponding hits due to noise and so was the mean value of the signal energy risetime and average frequency. Moreover, PLBs were contacted at the extent that accessibility and safety allowed us, with the produced profile over average frequency, amplitude, RMS, risetime, reverberation and initiation frequency mean-min-max values along with std where compared with the ones in the previously mentioned laboratory PLBs calibration signals and found to be close by.

The faced challenges were:

- How to actually place sensors in a safe way, eventually a technician mounted on the gate was used.

- To clean very well the points of sensor placement, finally performed with a cutting wheel equipped with griding plates.
- The power source was also important to obtain, and both solutions of AC power supply and a large 70000mAh powerbank were used successfully.
- The actual mounting on the movable gate of the Micro-SHM and the used cables. That was addressed very quickly with magnetic holders.

2.4.4.2 In site Validation and AE Data Acquisition on Italian Pilot Isola Serafini

On June of 2023, CERTH visited secondly another nearby Italian water-lock Isola Serafini Figure 47. Here a very simple and brief description of the visit will be performed as the reason of the visit was primary to feed the python code developed for the water-lock gate some data to validate the whole code. The actual recording gate-site of this water-lock can be seen at Figure 48.

Figure 47 Waterlock Isola Serafini overview, in ed circle the gate and place of the AE recordings

Figure 48 The actual gate (top left), the placement of the sensors red squares and the Micro-SHM (bottom right), the recording system (top right)

The sensors were placed by a technical from the water-lock firstly cleaning the point of placement on gate's metallic rod quite thoroughly, for the sensor to have a clean acoustic path to the underneath metallic path, and of course a gel couplant augmenting the acoustic conductance on that specific point of sensor placement.

The following experiments and recording were performed:

- Several open-close operations of the gates to record the acoustic emissions of normal gate operation.
- Several gate recordings of acoustic emissions on short gate operations with sudden stops as an attempt the normal operation of the gate for some reason to fail (a general failure).
- Various and multiple PLBs nearby sensors placements validating the good signal reception.

The faced challenges were:

- How to actually place sensors in a safe way, eventually a technician mounted on the gate was used.
- To clean very well the points of sensor placement, finally performed with a cutting wheel equipped with grinding plates.
- The power source was also important to obtain, and both solutions of AC power supply and a large 70000mAh powerbank were used successfully.
- Lastly due to size of the gates, as this water-lock was quite big it was not possible to open the gate even with a 10cm water height difference between the two sides of the gate, as some control security sentinels prohibited that. So acoustic emission recordings on water leakage was not possible
- The actual mounting on the movable gate of the Micro-SHM and the used cables. That was addressed very quickly with magnetic holders.

2.4.4.3 In site Validation and AE Data Acquisition on French Pilot Lyon Couzon Lock

On June of 2023, CERTH visited a French water-lock Lyon Couzon Lock Figure 49. Here a very simple and brief description of the visit will be performed as the reason of the visit was primary to feed the python

code developed for the water-lock gate some data to validate the whole code. The actual recording gate-site of this water-lock can be seen at Figure 50.

Figure 49 Couzon's Lyon water-lock overview , in red circle the position of the measured gate

Figure 50 The actual gate (top left), the placement of the sensors red squares (bottom left), the Micro-SHM (top right).

The sensors were placed by a technical from the water-lock firstly cleaning the point of placement on gate's metallic rod quite thoroughly, for the sensor to have a clean acoustic path to the underneath metallic path, and of course a gel couplant augmenting the acoustic conductance on that specific point of sensor placement.

The following experiments and recording were performed:

- Several open-close operations of the gates to record the acoustic emissions of normal gate operation.
- Several gate recordings of acoustic emissions on short gate operations with sudden stops as an attempt the normal operation of the gate for some reason to fail (a general failure).
- Various and multiple PLBs nearby sensors placements validating the good signal reception.

The faced challenges were:

- How to actually place sensors in a safe way, eventually a technician mounted on the gate was used.
- To clean very well the points of sensor placement, finally performed with a cutting wheel equipped with grinding plates.
- The power source was also important to obtain, and both solutions of AC power supply and a large 70000mAh powerbank were used successfully.
- The actual mounting on the movable gate of the Micro-SHM and the used cables. That was addressed very quickly with magnetic holders.
- Some gate control sentinels prohibited to have height difference of water over the two sides of the gate in order to mimic a water leakage.

Limitations and identified solutions for AE are further discussed in Appendix II.

2.4.5 AE First steps towards predictive Python Models Validation

It is worth mentioning here that the recordings in the sites were at first level used to validate the AE apparatus configuration as to provide the required repeatability and sensitivity capturing cracks inside the metallic structure of the gate and. This validation was furthered enhanced by direct PLBs performed closeby sensors location which I remind the reader as previously stated is the standard way of calibrating and validating an AE sensor. Of course, the actual models part of the inference system are still under development , their development is part of the D5.2 and these data will also be used to validate them. In short, the overall structure of the models consists from two parallel models. The **first** one capturing and detecting microcracks as an output of an autoencoder previously trains with PLBs training learning space part, produced from the laboratory testing PLBs and the water-lock site PLBs. For that validation purpose a validation sub dataset taken from the overall PLB learning space will be used, which is the standardized way of validating neural nets along with the required metrics of accuracy, recall and precision and so on so forth. The **second** model with the ability to learn the normal operation and producing alerts if time persistent out of the normal operation indications appear will use the recordings over gate's normal operation to train. The emulated for failure AE recordings (sudden gate open close) will be used to validate that indeed the system produces persistent operation points out of the ordinary.

3. CRISTAL Data Management System

This section presents the evolution of the data management concept presented within D2.1.

Data management work is related to WP5 and in particular to T5.1 and T5.2. As the discussions regarding the data storage resulted that final decisions should take place at the same time as the data distribution will be decided within T5.2, both will be described by D5.2. As those tasks are ongoing at time of submission of this deliverable, within this chapter the current status of the data acquisition architecture will be described. A finalization of this version will be discussed at submission of D5.2.

3.1. CRISTAL Data Store Architecture

The detailed elaboration on the topic of data storage will follow during the project in Task 5.2 of Work package 5 in Deliverable 5.2 and has therefore not yet been fully finalised. At this stage, however, it can be stated that there are different categories of data, which must also be handled and stored accordingly. For example, there is data that originates from other data sources and does not have to be passed on or even saved throughout the entire project. This includes, for example, information on historical water levels that is already stored externally and can be (and remains) retrieved at any time. The focus in terms of data sources is therefore on the pilots in the following. Although the development of the Data management system is still in progress the approach that will be used can be seen at Figure 51. As Data Management the HTTP REST API technology was selected. REST API HTTP offers a robust and versatile approach for receiving and managing large data volumes online. Its key benefits include:

- **Scalability:** The stateless nature of HTTP and the modular design of REST APIs enable them to handle massive data transfers efficiently, scaling effortlessly to accommodate increasing data loads.

- **Flexibility:** REST APIs leverage standardized HTTP methods (GET, POST, PUT, DELETE) for various data operations, making them adaptable to diverse data exchange scenarios.
- **Interoperability:** Adherence to HTTP protocols and common data formats (JSON, XML) allows seamless integration with different applications and platforms, promoting data accessibility and collaboration.
- **Ease of Development:** Well-defined REST API standards and readily available development tools simplify the creation and integration of these interfaces, saving development time and resources.
- **Security:** HTTP supports authentication and authorization mechanisms like OAuth and API keys, ensuring secure data transfer and access control within the large-scale data management process.

As a storage media either PostgreSQL or Maria DB will be used. The following are true for both choices:

- **Scalability:** Excels at handling massive data volumes, allowing seamless horizontal scaling by adding additional servers to distribute the workload and ensure smooth performance under high traffic.
- **Robustness:** Its robust architecture designed for high availability minimizes downtime and data loss, guaranteeing consistent access and reliability even during peak loads.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** As an open-source database, offers a significant cost advantage compared to proprietary alternatives, making it an attractive option for large-scale data management.
- **Object-Relational Features:** It extends beyond just relational capabilities, allowing for complex data structures and object-oriented programming elements, enhancing data modeling flexibility for intricate data requirements.
- **Advanced Indexing and Query Optimization:** Employs various indexing techniques and query optimization strategies, enabling efficient retrieval of specific information from large datasets, even with complex queries.

Overall, MariaDB's or PostgreSQL's scalability, robustness, cost-effectiveness, and advanced features make it a compelling choice for online data storage of large quantities, handling high traffic, and maintaining operational balance. More will be given at D5.1.

According to initial findings, the SMACK technology stack mentioned in the task description may be too powerful and too focussed on big data. The acronym SMACK stands for the following technologies: Spark, Mesos, Akka, Cassandra and Kafka. It is a technology stack that enables big data processing, real-time processing and scalability. There are some advantages and disadvantages to using this technology that need to be analysed in more detail. However, in the first approach there is no need to support real-time processing on a large scale with big data and therefore the use of the entire technology stack does not seem appropriate. The solution provided in Figure 51 takes into an account robustness, traffic balancing, modularity, deployability, high traffic handling, medium to large data storage queries, and available processing power over the incoming data if this of course is required, makes the selected Data Management and Data Storage solution for more attractive for the specific CRISTAL case than SMACK. This adoption is further augmented that the sensor data providers will in site inference on predictive failure alerts using simple but efficient and robust JSON traffic.

Figure 51 The used Data management and Data Storage approach

Based on the DIKW (Data, Information, Knowledge, Wisdom) pyramid, a layered data flow model has been created, which will be further specified and customised in the project in Task 5.2 as an ongoing process. Currently we have a data source layer, information layer and the knowledge layer.

The lowest layer, i.e. the data layer, basically includes the pilots planned for implementation as part of the project and the technologies and data sources necessary for the operation of DT and the SCMS system.

The intermediate layer is the information layer, the purpose of which is to process input data so that they acquire a specific context. Depending on this purpose, data processing can involve different operations such as combining different sets of data (aggregation), ensuring that the collected data is relevant and accurate (validation), etc.

The knowledge layer contains functionalities whose purpose is to process the collected data and information to obtain specific conclusions of business value.

As you can see from Figure 52, this layer handles data transfer on the one hand and the connected database or databases for storing necessary information on the other. This means that the data from the pilots and in particular the sensor technologies originate from the lowest layer and are forwarded to or collected by this layer. The Data Broker or as specified inside the GA Data Warehouse, can be understood as a data bus or a common unified data exchange mechanism operating in the same way and used by all project partners to communicate with all data sources from pilots. This means that any system, not just the DTs and the SCMS, can retrieve and receive data via this mechanism. It is an open system that can be expanded in both directions.

This is because both receiving and processing systems and software can be connected in this way, as can other sensor technologies or, more fundamentally, transmitting sensors and systems. However, it must

be clearly emphasised at this point that, as a rule, nothing or not much can be done with the data as long as it is not known how this data is to be processed.

In the case of the AE system, for example, the data processing takes place at the pilot site including any data mining and feature extraction, while the inference on failure notice or water lock gate prediction failure can either be also in pilots' site or as part / module of the digital twin; therefore the AE Data Warehouse data can be interpretable or vectors of features not yet inferred to prediction failure confidence level; due to the expertise and complexity required by CRISTAL's sensor technology providers in data mining and extraction, the solution of making the failure prediction on the waterlock site and exchanging with the Data Management JSONs messages on failure prediction was taken.

The data storage system is connected to this. This is used exclusively to store the sensor data and not to store duplicate information that is already available and accessible at any time, such as weather data. Redundancies should be avoided in this way. In realisation, this will be a database, collecting data from all pilots for later processing, analytics, etc. Depending on the data, different realisations can make sense here. The best-known types are probably SQL and non-SQL databases connected with discussions about structured and unstructured data and the complexity of queries. However, considering the currently agreed and expected formats (a lot of JSON) and the rather low frequency of transfers, other implementations such as document databases (e.g. CouchDB, MongoDB) seem to be more suitable. However, the entire topic is still being investigated in WP5 in Task 5.2 and has not yet been finalized. According to initial findings, the SMACK technology stack mentioned in the task description may be too powerful and too focussed on big data. The acronym SMACK stands for the following technologies: Spark, Mesos, Akka, Cassandra and Kafka. It is a technology stack that enables big data processing, real-time processing and scalability. There are some advantages and disadvantages to using this technology that need to be analysed in more detail. However, in the first approach there is no need to support real-time processing on a large scale with big data and therefore the use of the entire technology stack does not seem appropriate. However, a final decision regarding the specific implementation is still pending.

For the sake of completeness, it should be mentioned here that the realisations of the DTs also have separate databases. However, additional information such as the dimensions of locks or results from calculations are stored in these databases, i.e. enriched or processed data.

Figure 52 CRISTAL smarted architecture

The development of the communication and forwarding of data via the various layers and systems is to be developed step by step. The following use case would be conceivable as an example and is to be tackled or is already being partially coordinated and even implemented. So, step by step it could be done like this:

The associated digital twin receives or retrieves the data directly from AE System. This means that there is direct communication via interfaces and no integration of a data broker or another system.

In the second step, communication is established between the DTs and the SCMS. This is to be realised via a messaging system (e.g., RabbitMQ), very similar to a larger data broker. The advantage here is initially a small, separate realisation and communication between two systems instead of using a sensor technology and the exchange of JSON data is simpler and more manageable at this point.

In the third step, the data from the AE system can then be distributed to the DT via this very system (e.g. RabbitMQ).

This would show that communication between a sensor technology, a digital twin and the SCMS is possible via a data broker realisation. Furthermore, corresponding findings for the overall system can be gained from this prototypical implementation and taken into account accordingly in subsequent steps.

3.2. CRISTAL Data Set Structure

Different formats and types have already been discussed for data exchange. This has resulted in a large overview in which the sources of the data for the DTs and the SCMS are listed, which also affects the communication between DTs and SCMS, as well as which processing steps take place in which system. At least at a high overview level.

Essentially, the JSON format was defined and described as the exchange format on this basis. There are detailed descriptions such as the names and types of the respective data exchanges. Figure from 53 to 55 reports some examples related respectively to: ice cover thickness;

```
"ice_thickness": {  
    "location": {  
        "lon": "17.655843",  
        "lat": "52.795432"  
    },  
    "timestamp": 1701835314,  
    "value": 1.28,  
    "iso_uom": "MTR"  
},
```

Figure 53 Example of message related to ice thickness in JSON format

```
{  
  "ship_data": {  
    "callsign": "LX2279"  
    "vessel_type": "Tanker",  
    "length_m": 135,  
    "width_m": 12,  
    "draught_m": 1.6,  
    "departure_time": 1701835314,  
    "origin": "NLBOT"  
    "destination": "BEANR",  
    "speed_kn": 10.4  
    "tonnage": 560,  
    "capacity": 500,  
    "height_m": 12,  
    "cargo_weight_t": 470,  
    "cruising_speed_kn": 10,  
    "delays": "???"  
  },  
}
```

Figure 54 Example of message related to vessel characteristics in JSON format

```
{
  "water_level": {
    "location": {
      "lon": "17.655843",
      "lat": "52.795432"
    },
    "timestamp": 1701835314,
    "value": 1.28,
    "threshold": 2.4,
    "iso_uom": "MTR"
  },
  "water_flow_volume": {
    "location": {
      "lon": "17.655843",
      "lat": "52.795432"
    },
    "timestamp": 1701835314,
    "value": 123.28,
    "iso_uom": "MTQ"
  },
  "water_flow_velocity": {
    "location": {
      "lon": "17.655843",
      "lat": "52.795432"
    },
    "timestamp": 1701835314,
    "value": 15.7,
    "iso_uom": "KMH"
  },
  "infrastructure_status": [
    {
      "location": {
        "lon": "17.655843",
        "lat": "52.795432"
      },
      "status": "normal operation",
      "maintenance_schedule": [
        {
          "infrastructure_id": "idu/12/r",
          "start_time": 1701835314,
          "finish_time": 1701935314
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 55 Example of message related to navigability and infrastructure characteristics in JSON format

This defines the standard and the data to be sent and received by the JSON structure. A certain degree of flexibility and openness is of course retained in order to be able to add and supplement additional information, for example. Furthermore, as things stand at present, it cannot be assumed that all information can be sent in this form. For example, videos or graphics are also available from the SIR system

that are relevant for the implementation of the DT Smart Monitor. Nevertheless, this description defines the data exchange and thus forms the basis for communication between sensor technologies, the DTs, the SCMS and possibly other systems. Below is an example of the structure and information content of data that will be delivered to superior systems, i.e. DT, and indirectly to SCMS.

3.3. CRISTAL End-User Interfaces

As in the previous chapters the functionalities of the sensor technologies as well as the data storage and distribution were described, this section provides a short overview about the user Digital Twin interfaces, DTs, which will provide the information based on these data to the end users of the pilot use cases.

In CRISTAL project, the digital twin DT functions both for direct administration of the results from sensor values and for forwarding collected results to the SCMS. Direct administration by local operators requires access via a user interface.

For each pilot and the corresponding use cases an individual instance of a digital twin is planned. Within these three DTs, the sensor technologies will also be integrated differently in order to be able to map all relevant use cases defined in CRISTAL.

Therefore, each DT will produce slightly different output messages and due to the different use cases different interfaces will be needed, namely:

French Pilot: This pilot focuses on the possibility to use locks to pass. As this is mainly influenced by maintenance and malfunctions of the locks and therefore the closing of a lock determines whether a river section is navigable. The interface designed for this use case displays the locks (Figures 56 and 57) as well as important messages and documents of the locks. In addition, maintenance schedules must be visualized so that the passability of locks can be determined. The sensor technologies used to identify possible risks of malfunctions are the AE system and the Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR). Alerts based on this data as well as planned maintenance can be checked and edited with the interface.

Italian Pilot: This use case mainly focuses on the risk of decreasing navigability caused by sand banks. Therefore, this interface focuses on the river PO and different sections of it. Therefore this interface will mainly show the river, predicted information about water- and sandlevel as well as relevant indicators which could have an impact on those (Figure 58). A sensor technology which addresses the elicitation of sand dune heights is the fiber optic sensor. As those sensors are not installed in real environment, this interface will not support data outcome of them. A machine learning model based on weather data, water level and historic data of sand heights will be provided to close this gap. Also similarly to the French pilot there is an interest to check the The sensor technologies used to identify possible risks of malfunctions are the AE system maintenance and malfunctions of the locks (Figure 57)

Polish Pilot: Similar to the Italian pilot this pilot focuses on the navigability of the whole river or rather river sections. In contrast to the Italian pilot, within this pilot various river measurements are taken using the smart buoys. The interface should be able to show the relevant sections of the river and the position of the buoys. The view here is similar to the interface of the Italian case, but includes other measured values and does not include the sandlevel (Figure 58).

The DT lock interface has several pages to provide different information on all saved locks, the detailed information of specific locks as well as different entries of maintenance operations and possible malfunctions. Please be also aware that the shown data are mock data, as the DT are not in use at the point of submission.

Figure 56 displays an overview of lock entries where the name, location and the operating status can be seen. Based on this overview, overviews of maintenance operations and malfunctions are also provided, which give the option of listing the duration, affected areas of a lock and associated documents.

Figure 56 DT User interface - lock overview

The displayed entries can be viewed in detail as shown in Figure 57. The greyed placeholder within this view will be filled with a visualization of the respective lock and processed information based on the SIR and AE sensors.

Figure 57 DT user interface - Lock Detail

The DT focusing on the navigability of river sections has accordingly a very different user interface. Figure 58 shows the actual prototype of the ongoing development. This interface is structured with maps to show the geographical location of a river section. Also, the position of different weather stations can be checked here. Based on the selection of sections and the respective time periods, the forecasts for existing water heights, the height of sand deposits and the navigability of the sections are displayed accordingly. That information will be estimated based on weather data, water discharge of the river and historical data about sand heights. By displaying this weather data, the user should also be able to interpret the forecasts.

Figure 58 DT user interface – Waterlevel

It is worth highlighting that Figures from 56 to 58 are intended to provide a preliminary impression of the DT user interfaces. At the time of submission of this deliverable, the definition and development of the DTs user interfaces has not yet been finalised. At the time of CRISTAL project completion, there will be, in total two different types of DT Smart Monitors, one monitor for viewing locks and one monitor for entire river sections and their natural parameters such as water level. However, the latter type of monitor will be implemented with different sensors in the two pilots, resulting in some differences in the actual collection of information and, accordingly, its display. The sensor technologies and data provided to the DT which will be the basis for the DT generated information were described in Section 2 of this deliverable.

It is also worth mentioning and highlighting that further to the DT end-user interface and a GUI for the SCMS platform will be developed as part of WP3 activities. Within CRISTAL the sensor technologies and their output data are used to feed to different service systems: the DTs and the SCMS. While the DT's Smart Monitor is aimed at direct infrastructure operators, the SCMS is aimed at logistics service providers. This also implies that the Smart Monitor includes other information that is not required for the planning of consignment routes. Therefore, different DTs and their user interfaces focus on specific sensor technologies and their outputs, the SCMS will collect process and display the ones that are relevant for logistic purposes. The realization and implementation of the SCMS GUI will be described in WP3's Deliverable. However some details on how The data exchange between DT and SCMS will work is described within the previous section of this Deliverable D2.2 as well as in Deliverable D5.2.

4. Conclusions

D2.2 provided a proof of concept of CRISTAL sensor-based technologies (realized as part of Task 2.1 and Task 2.2) of their internal data acquisition system (Task 2.3) and how this is connected with the data management system to be developed as part of Task 5.2, as well as of CRISTAL end-users interfaces (Task 2.4). The activities reported in D2.2 fully fulfil the CRISTAL project milestone MS4 as far as the technical aspects of the CRISTAL technologies are concerned. In particular:

- Fiber Optic Sensor System (FOS)
 - the conceptual design and realization of the FOS System has reached a TRL5
 - the proof-of-concept testing has been run in laboratory; the results of the laboratory tests have confirmed the effectiveness of FOS to detect, in real time, the accumulation of sand-dunes and debris that might impare or create issues to the navigability.
- Smart Buoy System (SB)
 - The conceptual design on how the SB will be realized by assembling different components, all commercially available at TRL 9, has been finalized. Plans are in place for the proof-of-concept testing that will be conducted both in laboratory and in real conditions targeting a TRL7 at the end of the project.
 - An outline of the SIR system's architecture, comprising of sensor data acquisition and processing functions has been provided.
- Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR)
 - A viable system architecture for practical lock wall subsurface inspection was developed and refined. The proposed Data Acquisition Subsystem considers: power, positioning, measurement, control and end user interfaces. In addition, the proposed Data Management Subsystem involves: local data storage, data analytics and data transfer to the digital twin and/or end user.
 - A provisional data structure and nomenclature for SIR system operations have been formulated to reduce the complexity of internal collaborative development within the SIR team for the Data Acquisition and Data Management subsystem modules, alongside external collaboration with the Digital Twin developers.
 - Schema for measurement and positioning automation has been refined through practical laboratory testing on the SUNDIAL apparatus, alongside remote automation of the radar measurement software Prism2 through use of REMMINA and PYAUTOGUI control methods, both implemented via a connected Raspberry Pi.
 - Integration of an RTK GNSS positioning feedback system has been practically achieved through interfacing of NTRIP caster service RTK2GO in U-Center Application (v23.08), with IP-conflict between the radar controller and 4G router mitigated through rerouting of the network access path.

- Bespoke augmentations to leading radar measurement simulation software gprMax, enabling execution of area scan simulations to emulate real world SIR measurements of arbitrary healthy/defective subsurface geometries have been successfully developed and tested. Output from gprMax simulations, alongside real-world radar measurements from Prism2, have been successfully converted and interfaced with the radar data processing toolkit GPRPy, which has in turn been successfully back-converted to human-readable ASCII text format to be interfaced with algorithms for 3D isosurface generation in current development by the SIR team.
- A workflow and associated concept design for full system implementation on a real-world lock wall has been presented and discussed, highlighting the importance of balance between physical system robustness and portability of the deployed apparatus during upcoming fabrication of the modular operating platform.
- Structure of data used and/or provided by the SIR system must enable the survey data to be correlated with the infrastructure, so that features of interest and estimations of the presence of any potential defect or voids identified in the survey can be correlated to their location within the structure of the lock.
- The processing and handling of the data within the DT must present the data to the end-user structural maintenance experts in such a way that they can easily understand the context of the data and make informed decisions about the criticality of the identified potential features, defects, or voids, and the necessary remedial actions.
- The SIR data handling, processing and output must be precisely aligned with the data handling, processing, and presentation in the DT, so that the SIR data can be presented as meaningful and useful data to the end user by the DT. This process of alignment will be continued and finalised in Task 5.2.
- Acoustic Emission System (AE)
 - the prototype realization of the AE System is fully completed at TRL7
 - the prototype validation and testing is on-going in the French and Italian River Pilots. The tests will be concluded in full as part of Task 2.3 and they will be fully described in D2.3.
- CRISTAL Data Management System
 - the proof of concept of both the CRISTAL Data Store Architecture and CRISTAL Data Set Structure has been presented. The work to further develop as part of Task 5.2 and will be fully described in D5.2.
- CRISTAL End-Users Interfaces
 - prototypes of different user-interfaces for different use-case identified as of interest of the pilots in terms of waterways' navigability condition monitoring and lock infrastructure monitoring are ready and have been presented in D2.2. along with the ongoing developments.

The deliverable was developed in close and great collaboration between ENEA, EUROMOBILITA (EUMO), Newcastle University (UNEW), CERTH, L-PIT and Fraunhofer FHG; each one of the partners provided the content specific to the technology and/or system architecture they are developing.

No difficulties were encountered in the development of the content of the deliverable and therefore the same process adopted for D2.2 will be assumed as a good practice and implemented again for the writing of D2.3 that will see involved the same aforementioned teams.

D2.3 will describe CRISTAL sensor-based technologies validated in laboratory testing with stakeholders and submitted to the pilots for operational testing. D2.3 will describe also the integration of the CRISTAL sensor-based technologies developed by WP2 with other CRISTAL technologies, such as the Synchronodal Corridor Management Systems (SCMS) and Digital Twins (DT) developed in WP3 and WP5, respectively, and the integration, via interoperability, with other platforms already in use by the pilots, when possible. D2.3 will describe CRISTAL sensor-based technologies provided to the river pilots for operational testing.

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6. Appendices

Appendix I. Smart Buoy System (SB): Components' Technical specifications

- **DST810 Smart™ Multisensor with Gen2 Paddlewheel**

Depth, Speed-Through-Water, Water Temperature, Boat Attitude

The DST810 Smart Multisensor, featuring the Gen2 paddlewheel delivers speed-through-water data below 0.3 knots and is linear at 0.6 knots, maintaining accurate performance up to 45 knots. In addition to water temperature, depth and 5.7 Hz (5X per second) speed-through-water output with improved speed resolution, the DST810 features an integrated attitude sensor for heel and trim data.

Acoustic Window: Urethane

Attitude Sensor: Yes

Conventional Beam: 10°x44°

Data Rate: Depth: 1X/second, Speed: 5X/second, Heel/Trim: 10X/second

Functions: Depth, Speed, Temperature, Attitude

Hole Size: 51 mm (2")

Housing: Plastic

Hull Material: Fiberglass or metal

Max Deadrise: Up to 22°

Max Deadrise Angle: 22°

Max Depth: 0.5 m (1.6') to 100 m (330')

Mounting Style: Low Profile Thru-Hull

NMEA 2000 LEN: 3

Power Rating: 100 W

Protocol Output: NMEA 2000®

Pulses: 20,000 p/nm* (5.6 Hz per knot)—*p/nm = pulses per nautical mile

Retractable housing: Yes

Retrofits: Fits most Airmar 2" housings

Speed Range: Up to 45 knots

Temperature Accuracy: ±0.5°C (±1.8°F)

Tilted Element: No

Usable Shaft Length: 57 mm (2.25")

Voltage: 9 to 16 VDC

Water Temperature: -10° to 40°C (14° to 104°F)

Weight: 0.9 kg (2 lb.)

- **AIRMAR WeatherStation 200WX - wind speed & direction, air temp & humidity**

The WeatherStation 200WX is a durable, rugged, small housing sensor, that is IPX6 rated. The 200WX calculates the dynamic true wind speed and direction based upon the apparent wind (the wind you would feel on your hand if you held it out while moving), speed of the vehicle, and vehicle heading. Its internal 10 Hz GPS and three-axis electronic compass provide heading, position, speed-over-ground, and course-over-ground functionality that is necessary for dynamic true wind-data processing on a moving vehicle. The 3D compass with dynamic stabilization provided by the three-axis rate gyro enhances the rate-of-turn data. The patented 200WX maintains dynamic compass performance in hilly and mountainous terrain—common in military situations.

Ultrasonic measurement of apparent and Dynamic true wind speed and direction

Barometric pressure

Air and wind chill temperature

Relative humidity (field serviceable option)

Calculated dew point and heat index

GPS position, speed over ground, and course over ground

Three-axis, solid-state compass with dynamic stabilization

Three-axis rate gyro supplies rate-of-turn data

Three-axis accelerometer for best-in-class pitch and roll information

Housing IPX6 rated for water-ingress protection

Data output via a single cable (various lengths available)

NMEA 0183/ASCII serial data protocol over RS-232 interface

NMEA 2000 protocol over CAN

- **RR30.DA00-GGPI.9VF Radar distance measuring sensors**

General data:

Scanning range Sd: 0,5 ... 60m

Scanning range close limit Sdc: 0,5 ... 60 m

Scanning range far limit Sde: 0,5 ... 60 m

Version: IO-Link dual channel

Repeat accuracy: 1mm

Response time ton: < 80 ms

Release time toff: <80 ms

Temperature drift <+-10mm (Full Scale)

Power – up drift compensated after 20 min

Adjustment: IO-Link

Light indicator: LED yellow

Power o indicator: LED green

Carrier frequency: 122 ... 123 GHz

Band width: 1 GHz

Range resolution: 500 mm

Linearity error: +-10mm

Modulation Type: FMCW

Transmitting power (EIRP): < +20 dBm

Aperture angle: 6°

MTF: 126 years

Approvals certificates:

Ecolab

FCC / CFR-47 part 15 (USA)

RSS-210 Issue 10 (Canada)

EN 305 550-1 V.1.2.1 (European Union)

EN 305 550-2 V.1.2.1 (European Union)

Electrical data:

Voltage supply range +Vs: 12 ... 30 VDC

Current consumption max (no load): 200 mA

Short circuit protection: Yes

Reverse polarity protection: Yes, Vs to GND

Output circuit: IO-Link / push-pull

Output current: 100 mA, 50 mA (out 2)

Voltage drop Vd <2.5 VDC

Mechanical data:

Design: Cylindrical threaded

Housing material: Stainless steel 1.4404 (V4A)

Width / diameter: 30 mm

Height / length: 107 mm

Connection types: Connector M12

Ambient conditions:

Operating temperature: -40 ... +65 °C

Storage temperature: -40 ... +85 °C

Protection class: IP 68/69K & proTect+

Communication interface:

Interface: IO-Link V1.1

Baud rate: 230,4 kBaud (COM 3)

Cycle time: ≥ 4 ms

Process data length: 208 Bit

- **TF03-100 LiDAR 0,5 deg angle**

Benewake LiDAR TF03.

Lidar TF03-100 sensor specifications

Supply voltage: 6 V to 24 V

Current consumption:

≤ 200 mA @ 6 V

≤ 100 mA @ 12 V

≤ 50 mA @ 24 V

Photobiological safety: Class1 (EN60825)

Measuring range:

for 90% reflectance: 0.1 to 100 m

for 10% reflectance: 0.1 to 40 m

for 90% reflectance and 100 k lux: 0.1 to 80 m

for 10% reflectance and 100 k lux: 0.1 to 30 m

Accuracy

up to 10 m: ± 10 cm

from 10 m: 1%

Resolution: 1 cm

Repeatability: 1σ : < 3 cm

Operating frequency: 1 Hz to 1000 Hz (default: 100 Hz)

Light beam length: 905 nm

Operating angle 0.5°

Degree of protection: IP67
Corrosion resistant
Resistant to contamination
Immune to ambient light up to 100 klux
Operating temperature: -25°C to 60°C
Storage temperature: -40°C to 85°C
Communication: RS485/RS232
Cable length: 70 cm
Dimensions: 44 x 43 x 32 mm
Weight: 80 g

- **Leddar IS16**

Detection range: 0 to 50 meters
Accuracy (cm): +-5
Beam width: 45°, height: 7.5°
Data refresh rate (Hz): Up to 50
Operating temperature range (°C): -40 to +50
Eye safety: IEC 62471:2006 (exempt lamp classification)
Acquisition: 16 detection segments simultaneously (width 2.8°, height 7.5°)
Distance precision (mm): +-6 mm
Distance resolution (mm): +-10
Ingress protection rating IP67
Power consumption (W): 5,6
Regulatory compliance: CE, FCC, RoHS
Field of view: Horizontal 48, vertical 6
Discrete output: 2x PNP/NPN
Analog output: 4-20 mA, 0-10V
Interfaces: USB, RS-485, CAN
Wavelength (nm): 940
Power supply (VDC): 12 – 30
Dimensions (mm): 136 (H) x 86 (W) x 70 (D)
Weight (g): 430
Connector: M12
Display: optional control panel with LCD and 4 buttons

- **AIS EM-TRAK R300 RECEIVER**

AIS EM-TRAK R300 RECEIVER
Dimensions & weight: 140 x 100 x 50 mm (D x W x H), 280g
Data interfaces: Usb
Nmea2000®
IEC61162-1 (NMEA0183) output – 38400baud
IEC61162-1 (NMEA0183) input – 4800baud
Power: 12 or 24V DC
Power consumption: 150ma @12VDC, <2W average
Vhf receivers
Receiver 1 frequency: 161.975mhz
Receiver 2 frequency: 162.025mhz

Channel bandwidth: 25khz

Receiver sensitivity: <-107dbm @ 20% PER

Appendix II. Subsurface Inspection Radar System (SIR) Proof of Concept: Experimental procedures

Measurement Position Automation

Proof-of-concept testing for measurement position automation required the fabrication, programming, and setup of a NEMA style stepper motor with accompanying power transfer mechanism to advance the position of a radar measurement antenna at the input of user defined incrementation commands from an external microcontroller.

Two motors were trailed in the setup to gauge performance of more compact NEMA17 stepper motors for mechanical drive against more powerful, but also heavier NEMA34 stepper motors. Both motors were open loop for testing. Furthermore, the NEMA17 motor advanced the antenna and NEMA34 mount linearly via a timing belt drive mechanism whilst the NEMA34 rotated the antenna via direct coupling. Performance of each drive mechanism would also inform benefits and limitations to each approach when considering upscaling to the full scale Modular Operating Platform (A).

A total of 4x mechanical limit switches were also incorporated to the apparatus to allow the positioning system to home at start-up and stop the apparatus when extremal limits of translation and rotation were reached respectively.

The apparatus was designated SUNDIAL, owing to its rotational alignment of the antenna boresight vector in defining 3D local positioning coordinates. The physical assembly is pictured in Figure 59 the Positioning Unit (a) advances the radar antenna and second stepper motor attached to carriage (b).

Figure 59 SUNDIAL experimental rig: (a) Positioning Unit; (b) second stepper motor attached to carriage

It should be noted that this work was completed prior to the decision to adopt Impulse radar as the basis for the SIR system. Therefore, hardware featured is SFCW equipment from the tunnel subsurface inspection investigations previously mentioned in Section 2.3.2.3. This is why the test features 3D position defined by a single linear axis and antenna rotation, rather than the later adopted dual linear axis adopted by the automated Positioning Unit (A.2) of the refined SIR system. However, insight gained remains pertinent to development of the Modular Operating Platform (A) and has informed decisions made since.

Figure 60 shows the wiring diagram for SUNDIAL. An Arduino UNO microcontroller and was connected via UART to a windows PC running MATLAB 2022b facilitating real time user input of position commands and pre-scripting of movement patterns. This approach has since been updated to a single Raspberry Pi 3 Control Interface owing the more straightforward interfacing of GPIO inputs, display outputs and pre-scripting possible. The SIR development team has since undergone extensive training in python programming which has better facilitated development on a Raspberry Pi vs development in a combination of C and MATLAB syntax in the former method, considerably simpler to debug and flash for testing.

The Arduino UNO connected to the compact L829N stepper driver to interface with the NEMA17 motor and RTELLIGENT R86 Microstepper driver to control the more powerful NEMA34. Both controllers were mounted in a custom acrylic housing as shown in Figure 61. It was noted the screw terminal fixings of the R86 proved the more readily workable connection style than the Dupont connections of the L829N, which would often deform when mounted. To provide a consistent 5V reference voltage and energise logic circuits the R86 was connected to the Arduino in a common anode configuration. Movement is governed by two inputs, Signal and Direction. Setting direction HIGH or LOW dictated clockwise or anticlockwise rotation of the NEMA34 respectively when a steady Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal feeds the Signal line.

3D positioning and measurement capture of the radar antenna was successfully achieved on the SUNDIAL apparatus. Introducing additional grounding lines to the motor and support rail better suppressed electrical noise in the air launched GPR measurements recorded by the VNA, emphasising the importance of adding grounding lines to the upscaled SIR system's superstructure. The Arduino UNO's onboard code for motor control and limit switch reading required updates to incorporate debounce when reading limit switches to ensure false-positive triggers attributed to line noise did not prematurely halt the positioning process, and that false-negative triggers did not prevent the apparatus from stopping when extremal limits were reached.

It was found the NEMA17 would occasionally slip due to expansions and dents in the aluminium rail used, which would increase rolling resistance on the moving carriage containing the NEMA34 motor and antenna. Identifying this slip was achieved by eye. The team noted use of an odometer would better facilitate tracking of slip by providing verification of the true number of steps moved. Together, these points motivated the adoption of closed loop motors in the refined SIR system design to ensure any discrepancy between requested movement and delivered movement would be automatically compensated and a log of local position coordinates could be recovered from the encoders.

It was decided that NEMA34 motors provided the most practical approach to design refinement for the Positioning Unit (A.2) due to the eventual simplicity of interfacing the Microstepper driver with the microcontroller compared to the L298N. Furthermore, with the ambition to update to a closed loop system, this functionality was only commercially supported for NEMA23 and NEMA34 systems based on

Figure 61 Housing for SUNDIAL stepper motor control circuitry

The test of linear positioning considers a measurement system tracking along a horizontal axis only. On reflection and brainstorming for the revised two dimension XY plotter-style design of the positioning system, the SIR team decided leadscrews presented a more practical basis for the drive mechanism than timing belts given leadscrews can support the weight of the moving carriage when the machine is at rest (therein reducing the strain on the motors during holding) and can be readily applied to both horizontal and vertical motion.

Measurement Triggering Automation

Proof-of-concept test for automated measurement positioning naturally gave rise to testing for measurement triggering automation.

The measurement automation of the Subsurface Radar Unit (B.2) will be achieved using a Slave PC running Prism2 radar measurement capture software. In laboratory testing, the Slave PC was controlled remotely via Remote Desktop Connection (RDC) over a physical ethernet (LAN) connection to the Raspberry Pi 3 that forms the Central Interface of the Control Subsystem.

Lightweight automation was achieved using the REMMINA Remote Desktop Connection (RDC) module as shown in Figure 62 Prism2, running on Slave Windows 11 Pro PC (Figure 62**Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania.**a), is displayed via REMMINA's integrated interactive control interface (Figure 62b), which facilitates direct control of Prism2 via Raspberry Pi when cursor and keyboard peripheral automation via PYAUTOGUI scripting (Figure 62c).

Figure 62 Displays illustrating REMMINA automation

The automation process mandated installation of the Windows 11 Pro OS in place of a standard Windows 11 licence to enable remote desktop access to the machine. Use of the PYAUTOGUI module enables to create python scripts on the Pi 3 capable of repositioning the slave PC cursor alongside entering data and command keystrokes. Together, REMMINA and PYAUTOGUI facilitated full control of slave PC functionality in Prism2. The only challenge faced by this approach is the one-time derivation and input of on-screen coordinates for the cursor to position to control Prism2 via the REMMINA RDC window. In future refinement, it would be desirable to further automate this process by snapping the cursor to the nearest button in the REMMINA RDC preview window, circumventing the need for pixel level precision in the cursor positioning commands saving extensive programming time.

RTK GNSS Geolocation Recovery

For initial testing, the RTK functionality was disabled to simplify network architecture and establish both systems could effectively transfer data to the same host PC concurrently. This decision mitigated the requirement for connection to the internet as all key processes ran locally on the PC. Testing ran on a Lenovo IdeaPad Flex 5 (8GB RAM) laptop running Windows 11 Pro. Running the test on a consumer-grade PC demonstrated that computing resource demand for the data acquisition procedure was low enough for it to be run on such a device, and that specialist high-performance computing equipment wasn't required.

Initial tests physically connected the ethernet output of the Radar Controller to an TAMEZON ethernet-USB 3.0 adapter, with the zBELL antenna interfaced via USB. The option for positioning via External GPS was selected in the Prism2 configuration menu prior to measurement. For the purposes of trials, the 1GHz Zond 12 radar antenna was connected to the Radar Controller, together with the PC all elements were mounted to a shockproof cart supplied by Radar System Inc. to allow trial B-scan measurements to be taken of the pavements and road surfaces in vicinity of the laboratory as shown in Figure 63. The tests successfully demonstrated the zBELL antenna (with RTK disabled) could directly interface with Prism2 and assign global geolocation coordinates to B-scan measurement data.

Figure 63 Measurement Module (B) mounted on shockproof pushcart (a) passing global geolocation data to Prism2 (b)

Subsequent testing saw RTK functionality activated to increase the spatial resolution of the GNSS antenna from 1m to the order of 10mm. The test site was located in an area with large trees surrounding the site and with access to the internet that was known to be intermittent and have a moderate data-rate, therefore a significant increase in resolution on these tests was not expected to be observed. In this context, the primary objective was to demonstrate that the RTK connection remained stable, and the indicator light remained illuminated during B-scan measurement acquisition.

To facilitate internet access, a TP-Link M7350 Portable 4G Wireless Router was procured alongside a standalone Vodafone Mobile Data SIM with unlimited data allowance to provide internet connectivity for the trails, and potentially for integration with the finalised SIR system. The M7350 interfaced via micro-USB and when connected to the PC without the Radar Controller provided stable internet connectivity.

To enable RTK functionality, the U-Center Application (v23.08) was run alongside Prism2. The cloud based NTRIP Caster RTK2GO was selected to provide real time RTK correction data. Once linked to U-Center, the nearest local mount-point to the test site was selected as shown in Figure 64. The distribution of mount points throughout Europe is comparable to the UK. In both circumstances, the proximity of RTK mount points to test sites is sufficient for required RTK GNSS positioning resolution. To enable the zBELL to simultaneously communicate with U-Center and Prism2, a shared digital communication (i.e., “COM”) interface was virtually generated using HHD Software’s freeware “Virtual Serial Port Tools”. Prior to physically connecting the Radar Controller, the zBELL was connected to the PC running U-Center.

It was observed that the zBELL required approximately 1 minute to establish a GNSS signal stable to 5 decimal places, with an unobstructed 30-degree field of view on all sides. For laboratory testing, this warranted the system to be moved fully outdoors wherever possible, or for placement of the zBELL as close to a window as possible if indoors. This observation informed the decision to initially track the Modular Operating Platform (A)'s carriage horizontally at the top of the survey quadrant.

Figure 64 RTK mount points (provided by RTK2GO) to the test site at UNEW (yellow dot)

On activation of the RTK link, the GNSS signal stabilised at 6-8 decimal places subject to measurement location around the laboratory grounds, indicating a successful increase in geolocation positioning accuracy. The NTRIP connection indicator also displayed green on the U-Center GUI as shown in Figure 65. The RTK indicator LED onboard the zBELL antenna also switched from non-illuminated to a steady pulsation once RTK was enabled.

Figure 65 U-Center (v23.08) displays successful activation of the RTK NTRIP client (indicator highlighted in yellow)

This was consistent with expectations, as the RTK LED is designed to illuminate only when RTK correction is being performed, with a rest buffer of 1-2 seconds between each network update call. As seen in the real time network traffic monitoring in Figure 66, a periodic 24kbps receive peak is seen to occur approximately every 5 seconds, consistent with the observed pulsation of the RTK LED, evidencing successful RTK updates as desired.

Figure 66 DT user interface – Waterlevel RTK periodic network call results in regular receive peaks of approximately 24kbps

Complications arose when the Radar Controller was subsequently connected, with internet access being disabled the instant the ethernet cable was connected to the PC. It was established the Radar Controller and 4G Router had an IP-Conflict issue due to both devices effectively serving as self-contained local area networks. Therefore, it was decided to streamline the network architecture and replace the M7350 with

a TP-Link Archer AC750 to ensure all physical network connections were routed through the router and not through the TAMEZON USB interfaces or those of the PC itself. Through extensive debugging of the signal path hop-by-hop through the network, the following solution was devised to rectify the IP-conflict on an arbitrary host PC:

- Step 1. Physically connect only the Radar Controller to the host PC;
- Step 2. Open Windows command prompt and type `<ipconfig /all>` to list all network connections.
- Step 3. Record the Radar Controller's default gateway address (here 192.168.1.101)
- Step 4. Open Windows command prompt as an administrative user, type `<route -p add 192.168.0.10 mask 255.255.255.255 192.168.1.101>` hit enter (*). 2
- Step 5. To validate the IP-conflict is resolved, run `<ping [default gateway address]>` to check communication with the Radar Controller is established.

Step 6. Run `<ping www.google.com>` to validate communication with the external internet is established. If both pings are successful the system is in an operable state

Appendix III. Acoustic Emission Systems (AE): Limitations and Solutions

As in all engineering applied techniques, AE has some limitations and challenges associated with using AE technology for health status detection and failure prediction:

- Noise and False Alarms: AE sensors can be sensitive to environmental noise, leading to potential false alarms or difficulty in distinguishing relevant acoustic emissions from background noise, especially in high-noise industrial environments. This can be overcome with advanced ML wavelet denoising and statistical weighting of the output
- Sensor Placement and Calibration: Proper placement and calibration of AE sensors are crucial for accurate crack detection. In complex structures or in areas with limited accessibility, ensuring optimal sensor placement can be challenging. Although it is of a challenge, regarding the water-lock gates the points are pretty much dictated by the point the forcing electromechanical pistons connected to gate's leaves.
- Signal Interpretation: The interpretation of AE signals requires expertise to differentiate between various types of AEs and to accurately assess the severity and nature of the detected cracks. In our case this has been addressed by using advanced denoising techniques such as wavelet, bandwidth filtering and autoencoding neural nets.
- Data Analysis and Processing: The large volume of data generated by AE monitoring systems requires sophisticated analysis and processing techniques to effectively extract meaningful information and identify relevant acoustic emissions associated with crack initiation and propagation. This was addressed through a proprietary methodology of slotifying the AEs based

² This command directs ONLY the IP address 192.168.0.10 (Radar Controller) to the gateway 192.168.1.101 (Radar Controller's Internal Router Gateway). The mask is 255.255.255.255 to ensure it is ONLY that SINGLE address that gets routed. The -p ensures the route remains permanent and survives reboots.

on energy levels, risetime and average frequencies, assisted by high level of feature extraction both in spectral but also in time and statistical domain over slots and slots grouping per day.

- **Cost and Implementation:** The initial investment and operational costs associated with implementing AE monitoring systems, including sensor installation, data acquisition equipment, and analysis software, can be significant. Although what we are using regarding AE system is of research level still there are plenty of commercial AE systems in good price and of course the economy of scale cost can further reduce.
- **Integration with Structural Health Monitoring:** Integrating AE technology with existing structural health monitoring systems and protocols can pose technical and logistical challenges, particularly in retrofitting older structures. Although in many SHM cases this might be a case in water-lock gates due to the metallic nature of the construction itself the sensors can easily be deployed through magnetic holders.

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